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Database/structural model and report describing the relationships between functionality, physicochemical properties and hazard, and allowing for integration in the safe innovation approach

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1 Description of task

This deliverable is part of the task 3.2 which aims at 1) deriving the safety information needed to consider in a gate specific way, and 2) develop a data model and database that allows for comparison of safety and functionality considerations for physicochemical properties. For early gates, screening information giving guidance to avoid unacceptable risks is important, whereas at later gates information needs to be more quantitative and conclusive. At first, nanomaterial properties relevant for both, function and risk, will be identified by opposing the physicochemical properties of materials needed for their function and data on the safety aspects related to those properties which are described e.g. by data on toxicologically relevant endpoints. The basis for the toxicologically relevant information will come from the database already developed within the framework for NANoREG. The database provides data for the derivation of the relationship between physical chemical characterization and toxicity. It is intended to use the database developed within NANoREG including all data. The database is suitable to store data on physical chemical characterization, toxicity testing generated in other work packages. Upon development within NanoReg2, the database will also be suitable for the storage of data on the functionality of nanomaterials a task that was conceptually developed in T3.2, D3.3, and the working document on functionality of nanomaterials. Moreover, it is intended to investigate what aspects/tools developed within eNanoMapper can be of use. In order to comprise current and future materials, a scheme will be developed enabling integration of considerations for physicochemical properties related to safety and functionality for materials on increasing TRL.

Based on the information gathered in the TNO-NANoREG database, the database will be optimized for the NanoReg2 requirements of the stage gate model. Whereas the present database provides data for Structure Activity Relation (SAR) models for the relationship between structure and toxicity, integration with data on structure-functionality relationships and synthetic feasibility needs to be included in the next step. In principle, the SbD strategy should be open to include data collection/sharing from different disciplines and activities in the value chain. The guidance for the use of the database for SbD approached per gate will be developed to support go/no go decisions to be taken by the different actors in a gate (TNO, INM, TEMAS, RIVM, KI, FORTH). This task will be carried out in close collaboration with task 1.6.

2 Description of work & main achievements

2.1 Summary

According to the description of work, this deliverable (D3.2) aims to describe the database model/structure that contains information on physicochemical parameters and toxicity, and physicochemical parameters and functionality on the other hand. The database will help to gain insight into physicochemical parameters optimally leading to best achievable safety levels without compromising functionality. The first draft of D3.2 was delivered in month 12 which was subsequently updated in month 24. The present deliverable in month 36 is the final version.

Until M24, the database needs of all work packages have been defined and described in a document entitled "Analysis of the database needs and solutions". To fulfill the database needs of the NanoReg2 project, a NanoReg2 working group was established, the Database Solution Team. Within this team, one uniform, harmonized database solution for the entire NanoReg2 project was formed. Within the database solution team, it has been decided that the main structure of the database will be based on the FP7 eNanoMapper project database software and data model. The database architecture follows the decision proposed and agreed during Data Solution team meetings and consists of federated search architecture, integrating multiple project-specific instances of eNanoMapper database (doi:10.3762/bjnano.6.165). These databases offer user friendly web interface and application programming interface and use the same software as previously described in publications and eNanoMapper deliverables. The eNanoMapper database instances for NANoREG, NanoTest, MARINA and NanoGenotox data were installed and updated several times with the physical chemical properties and toxicity of nanomaterials provided by the relevant projects (FP7 NANoREG, FP7 MARINA, FP7 NanoTest and the NanoGenotox). The input parameters of 8 tools in the SIA toolbox which encompass the nanomaterials and information relating to their characterisation, as well as information describing relevant experimental paradigms and biological interactions were linked with the NanoReg2 database and their ontology references. On the similar grounds, the tool parameters, related to the nanomaterial exposure, were linked with NECID (Nano Exposure & Contextual Information Database). These 9 tools were LICARA NanoSCAN, GUIDEnano Tool, NanoSafer 1.1, Stoffenmanager nano, NanoRiskCat, Swiss Precautionary Matrix, Control Banding Nanotool, SUNDS and the Future nano Needs Bayesian belief network. The complexity level of the linking was kept at first level which provides the user with the relevant endpoints investigated that match with the meaning of the specific parameters in the tool. The input parameters of these tools were also mapped against the availability of their corresponding data in the two databases to find the data gaps. While the functionality of nanomaterials has been described using the NanOn ontology (T3.2 of the NanoReg2 project), the activities on how to effectively implement its link with the exposure data in the NanoReg2 database is still ongoing. The concept of nanomaterials functionality has been described in the Working Document of functionality, which will be integrated into the Safe Innovation Guidance Manual at the end of the project. A proposal of integration of such data has been suggested by INM (proposing a structural data model for functionality and its linkage to the physicochemical data already available), the feasibility to integrate such data into the eNanoMapper database has been discussed with and confirmed by IDEA.

In the present M36 version, a user guidance is included in the deliverable which furthers the complexity level of the linking between the input parameters and the databases to second level. At the second level, the information on actual assays that are relevant for the specific input parameter from the NanoReg2 database are provided and matched with the exact meaning of the parameter in the tool with input of INM. This is achieved by providing a user guidance which assists the user in deciding the most relevant assay for both the particular parameter and the type of the nanomaterial or product being assessed. It guides the user, step-by-step, in retrieving the data from the NanoReg2 database. Furthermore the link between the eNanoMapper database and NECID has been updated. The data in the NanoReg2 database has been extended with data on exposure originating from TNO exposure data in the NECID database structure.

2.2 Description of the work carried out

Task 3.2, safety aspects to be considered per stage gate, aims at deriving the safety information needed to consider in a gate specific way, and develop a structural model that allows for comparison of safety and functionality considerations for physicochemical properties. Based on the information gathered in the NANoREG database, the database is optimized for its structural model. Whereas the present database leads to structure activity relation (SAR) models for the relationship between structure and toxicity, integration with data on structure-functionality relationships and synthetic feasibility still needs to be included. A model for such a relationship has, however, been proposed by INM. In principle, the Safe-by-Design (SbD) strategy should be open to include data collection/sharing from different disciplines and activities in the innovation process. The data in the database needs to be translated into guidance for SbD approaches per stage gate, supporting go/no go decisions in each gate. Task 3.2 was carried out in close collaboration with Tasks 1.6 and 3.2. The deliverable describes the database model/structure that contains information on physicochemical characteristics and toxicity on one hand, and physicochemical characteristics and functionality on the other hand (Task 3.2). The database helps to gain insight into physicochemical properties optimally leading to best achievable safety levels without compromising functionality.

The executive board of NanoReg2 (NEB) has decided to form a Database Solution Team that is tasked with all database and data management issues in the project, in particular those which relate to WPs 1 to 4. Therefore D3.2 has been addressed by the Database Solution Team and harmonized with other NanoReg2 database activities. The Database Solution Team is led by Nina Jeliaskova (IDEA Consult) and other members are: Penny Nymark (KI), Peter Ritchie (IOM), Hubert Rauscher (EC) and Thies Oosterwijk (TNO). Andrea Haase (WP1 leader) is the contact person of the database solution team. The first activity is to define the database needs of all relevant work packages in NanoReg2. After this, the Database Solution Team will propose appropriate technical solutions to the NEB. The NEB will take a final decision concerning the proposals of the solution team and how to implement them. In Annex 1, a review is provided that compiles the data requirements and wishes of the four WPs in NanoReg2 which generate and use new and existing data to achieve their deliverables.

The database structure, as described in the NanoReg2 WP3 description of action, supports the safe innovation approach (SIA). In order to be able to use the database for the SIA, the needs for this database must be defined. Due to its specific application within the SIA, the database needs are dependent on SIA supporting specific tools. The tasks defined for D3.2 are summarized in Figure 1. The first step involved the selection of a first set of tools which constitute the SIA toolbox. This task was done in collaboration with the caLIBRAte and ProSafe projects and involved the participation of TNO, INM and RIVM as partners. An overview of these tools is provided in the section 3.1. Simultaneously, in collaboration with task 3.2 partners, 9 of these tools were identified in detail to describe their input parameters. These input parameters were linked with their ontology references and the experimental databases which encompass the nanomaterials and information relating to their characterisation, as well as information describing relevant experimental paradigms and biological interactions (see Annex 2). The level of detail at which the input parameters were linked, is discussed in Annex 3. While the linking of input parameters with their ontology references ensures that the used terminologies are harmonized, their linking with experimental databases e.g. NanoReg2 and NECID allows a user to retrieve the experimental data corresponding to the tools' input parameters.

	TASK	PARTICIPANTS		STATUS
○	1. Define first set of tools to be used in SIA toolbox	TNO, INM, RIVM (collaboration with Calibrate, ProSafe)	✓	See section 3.1
○	2. Describe input parameters for each tool	Task 3.2 partners	✓	See Annex 2
○	3. Define level of detail at which the ontology and database should be linked to the SIA toolbox	TNO, INM, RIVM, Database solutions team	✓	See Annex 3
○	4. Link SIA input parameters with the database structure and ontology	Task 3.2 partners	✓	See Annex 3
○	5. Develop user guidance to find specific data	Task 3.2 partners	✓	See section 3.2

Figure 1: Activities defined for D3.2

The NanoReg2 database architecture follows the decision proposed and agreed during Data Solution team meetings and is illustrated in Figure 2. The bottom panel describes there are multiple installations (instances) of eNanoMapper database (doi:10.3762/bjnano.6.165), populated with specific projects data. These databases offer user friendly web interface and application programming interface and use the same software as previously described in publications and eNanoMapper deliverables. eNanoMapper database instances with content from NANoREG, NanoTest, MARINA and NanoGenotox data were installed and updated several times. Databases setup and data population was performed within WP1 T1.6. A NanoReg2 specific eNanoMapper database instance was installed during the last 6 months and further populated with exposure data provided by TNO.

At the top, the four screenshots with captions eNanoMapper, NANoREG, caLIBRAte and NanoReg2, representing the search applications, providing integrated view of selected sets of database instances, specific to the project. The web site at <https://search.data.enanomapper.net> provides entry points to all integrated search views.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 SIA toolbox and database gaps

The Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) consists of the integration of the SbD concept and the regulatory preparedness concept (D3.1). To assist industry with the implementation of the SIA, within NanoReg2 a SIA toolbox and a SbD implementation platform were developed. This set of tools is presented in Table 1. This deliverable addresses 9 of such tools included in the SIA toolbox. The database needs of the following 8 tools, have been identified in detail in this deliverable: (i) LICARA NanoScan; (ii) Swiss precautionary matrix for synthetic nanomaterials (at the time of writing); (iii) FutureNanoNeeds-Bayesian Belief Network; (iv) Control Banding Nanotool; (v) Stoffenmanager Nano; (vi) NanoRiskCat; (vii) Nanosafer CB; (viii) GuideNano Tool; (ix) SUNDS. As first part of the identification, the input parameters of each tool are enlisted in Annex 2. These input parameters were then mapped against the availability of the corresponding data in NanoReg2 and NECID databases.

Table 1: First draft of an overview of existing and newly developed tools which will be included in the SIA toolbox. Some of these tools will define specific database needs.; ^D: Database needs are defined in this deliverable; [?]: Under development, the use in the SIA is still under discussion as well as its potential database needs; ^{WP1}: Database needs are defined in WP1

Existing SIA tools	SIA tools developed within NanoReg2
ANSES: Control Banding Tool for Nanomaterials ^D	Checklist for safety information needed per gate [?]
Licara NanoScan ^D	Grouping approaches (wp1) ^{WP1}
The Swiss precautionary matrix for synthetic nanomaterials ^D	SIA Checklist [?]
Control Banding Nanotool ^D	Safety dossiers and safety profile (wp3) [?]
Stoffenmanager Nano ^D	Checklist for safety information needed per gate (wp3) [?]
NanoRiskCat ^D	
Nanosafer CB ^D	
Guidenano Tool ^D	
MARINA Risk Assessment Strategy	
Toolkit Dermal Exposure and Risk Management (RiskofDerm)	
NANOSOLUTIONS	
NanoFASE: NanoFASE model system	
NanoFASE: SimpleBox4Nano screening fate assessment model	
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	
AISE react (soap and detergent manufacturing industry)	
Consexpo Nano Tool	
British Aerosol Manufacturers Association (BAMA) model	
European Solvents Industry Group (ESIG) Generic Exposure Scenario (GES) Risk and Exposure Tool (EGRET)	
SprayExpo model (BAUA)	
dART (dermal advanced reach tool)	
One box-model for accident situations in laboratories (Walser et al 2012)	
DeRmal Exposure Assessment Method (DREAM)	
ECETOC TRA	
Future Nano Needs – Bayesian network (FNN-BNN) ^D	
SUNDS	

Such mapping paved the way for a fit-gap analysis between the input parameters and the two databases. It is shown in Table 2. Instead of showing individual input parameters, they are categorized in 15 classes in Table 2. Out of these 15 classes, 6 have no data available in either of the two databases. These classes are: Product application & conditions; Consumer Exposure; NM emission to the environment; Functionality; Nano-enabled product physicochemical properties; Market & societal benefits. It should be noted that a concept of integration of functionality aspects has been provided by INM within the work done in T3.2.

Table 2: Fit-gap analysis of data on input parameters of tools in the SIA toolbox in the NanoReg2 and NECID database.

Input parameter category	Example/description	Stoffen manager nano	LICARA nanoSCAN	NanoRisk Cat	FNN-BBN	Nano-Safer	Precautionary Matrix	GUIDE nano
Product general information	CAS, Catalogue no etc.	NanoReg2 NECID	NA	NanoReg2 NECID	NA	NanoReg2 NECID	NA	NanoReg2 NECID
Nanomaterial physicochemical properties	Particle size, shape, density etc.	NanoReg2 NECID	NanoReg2 NECID	NanoReg2 NECID	NanoReg2 NECID	NanoReg2 NECID	NanoReg2 NECID	NanoReg2 NECID
Medium Interaction	Solubility, surface charge etc.	NA	NanoReg2	NanoReg2	NA	NA	NanoReg2	NanoReg2
In vivo toxicity & metadata		NA	NanoReg2	NanoReg2*	NA	NanoReg2	NanoReg2	NanoReg2
In vitro toxicity & metadata		NA	NanoReg2	NA	NA	NA	NanoReg2	NanoReg2
Ecotoxicity & metadata	Bioaccumulation, persistence, oxygen depletion in water etc.	NA	NanoReg2	NanoReg2	NA	NA	NA	NanoReg2
Work area & conditions	Worker weight, amount handled, PROCs etc.	NECID	NECID	NA	NECID#	NECID	NECID	NECID
Local control measures and PPE	RMM, efficacy etc.	NECID	NECID	NA	NA	NA	NA	NECID
Worker exposure		NECID	NECID	NA	NECID#	NECID	NECID	NECID
Product application & conditions	FCs, market application etc.	NA			NA	NA	NA	
Consumer Exposure		NA		NA	NA	NA		
NM emission to the environment	Amount of NM emitted during production, use or disposal	NA			NA	NA		
Functionality		NA			NA	NA	NA	NA
Nano-enabled product physicochemical properties	Fraction of NM in the matrix, composite hardness, NM dispersion state etc.	NA	NA	NA		NA	NA	
Economic & societal benefits	Highly qualified labour force, expected purchase price etc.	NA		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
* NanoRiskCat and NanoSafer also uses toxicity information for bulk materials # FNN-BBN uses data for end of life only								

Grey: Input information is not required by tool, Green: Input information is required by tool and available in one of the databases/ontologies, Red: input information is required by tool but not available in any of the databases/ontologies.

2.3.2 NanoReg2 database user guidance

In this section, a guidance is provided to retrieve the data from NanoReg2 database for the input parameters (i.e. physico-chemical, toxicological, eco-toxicological, exposure and environmental fate related) of the tools in the SIA toolbox. For a given input parameter, there can be multiple assays in the database. This guidance, thus, assists a user to decide the most relevant assay(s) for a particular parameter. The workflow of the guidance is shown in Figure 4. Prior to the data retrieval from the database, the user guidance consists of three steps which successively filter the database to the final data of interest.

Figure 4: Workflow in NanoReg2 database user guidance

2.3.2.1 Material identification

The data retrieval process starts with the nanomaterial identification for which a user accesses the database. The data present in the NanoReg2 database (Figure 5 (a)) can be accessed by the knowledge of either

- (i) commercial name of the nanomaterial or
- (ii) type of the nanomaterial (core material/substance).

In the case of commercial names, at the time that this document was drafted, 30 such names have been assembled so far in the database which can be found by clicking the tab “Nanomaterial” on the left sided pane of the interface (see Figure 5 (b)). These commercial names are enlisted in Table 3 with the endpoints (or physicochemical properties) which are pre-known to a user (either through product data sheet or manufacturer’s website). The assay used to determine these endpoints are also provided in the parenthesis (if known). Out of these 30 nanomaterials,

- (i) 21 (i.e. 70%) correspond to the products from EU-JRC which are exhaustively characterized (also referred to as the JRC or OECD representative nanomaterials).
- (ii) 4 (i.e. PLGA-PEO nanoparticles, Endorem® Iron oxide nanoparticles, Rhodamine B and UPM Birch hardwood Pulp) do not have any pre-known physico-chemical property.
- (iii) 4 products (i.e. PL-A-Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, PL-M-Fe₃O₄, Mitsui-7 MWCNT and Cheap Tubes MWCNT) have minimal (2 or 3) pre-known properties.

These 30 commercial products are also present in terms of their core material in the database. In other words, the product for which a user accesses the database can also be identified by its core material. A list of 25 such core materials, with their respective ontology IDs, is provided in Table 4 for which data can be retrieved in the NanoReg2 database. They can be found under the tab “Nanomaterial type” (see Figure 5 (c)). Clicking a nanomaterial (or type of the nanomaterial) of interest filters the database corresponding to this nanomaterial (or type of the nanomaterial).

Figure 5(a) shows a screenshot of the NanoReg2 database search results. The search criteria are set to 'multi-walled carbon nanotube'. The results list four entries:

- JRCNM04000a (NM-400 (Multi-walled carbon nanotubes)) multi-walled carbon nanotube**: Results include TOX.Repeated dose toxicity - oral, TOX.Genetic toxicity in vitro, TOX.Cell Viability, P-CHEM.Impurities, P-CHEM.Aspect ratio/shape, P-CHEM.Particle size distribution (Granulometry), P-CHEM.Specific surface area, P-CHEM.PC_THERMAL_STABILITY_SECTION.
- JRCNM04001a (NM-401 (Multi-walled carbon nanotubes)) multi-walled carbon nanotube**: Results include P-CHEM.Impurities, TOX.Repeated dose toxicity - oral, TOX.Genetic toxicity in vitro, P-CHEM.Specific surface area, P-CHEM.Particle size distribution (Granulometry), P-CHEM.Aspect ratio/shape, TOX.Cell Viability, P-CHEM.PC_THERMAL_STABILITY_SECTION.
- JRCNM04002a (NM-402 (Multi-walled carbon nanotubes)) multi-walled carbon nanotube**: Results include TOX.Repeated dose toxicity - oral, P-CHEM.Specific surface area, TOX.Genetic toxicity in vitro, TOX.Cell Viability, P-CHEM.Particle size distribution (Granulometry), P-CHEM.PC_THERMAL_STABILITY_SECTION, P-CHEM.Impurities, P-CHEM.Aspect ratio/shape.
- NRCWE-006 (MWCNT (Mitsui)) multi-walled carbon nanotube**: Results include TOX.Repeated dose toxicity - oral, P-CHEM.Particle size distribution (Granulometry), TOX.Genetic toxicity in vitro, P-CHEM.Impurities, TOX.Cell Viability, P-CHEM.Specific surface area, P-CHEM.Aspect ratio/shape, P-CHEM.PC_THERMAL_STABILITY_SECTION.

Figure 5(b) shows a screenshot of the NanoReg2 database search results with filters applied. The search criteria are 'multi-walled carbon nanotube'. The filters include:

- Projects (120704)
- Study providers (120396)
- Nanomaterial type (119878)
- Nanomaterial (113990)
- Protocols (352729)
- Method (283018)
- TOX (315459)
- P-CHEM (37872)
- ECOTOX (1197)
- EXPOSURE (120)
- Cell (284748)
- Species (39578)
- Exposure route (4117)
- Medium (78003)
- Dispersion protocol (81886)
- Experiment year (120704)
- References (120086)
- Release (120704)

Figure 5(c) shows a screenshot of the NanoReg2 database search results with filters applied. The search criteria are 'multi-walled carbon nanotube'. The filters include:

- Projects (120704)
- Study providers (120396)
- Nanomaterial type (119878)
- Nanomaterial (113990)
- Protocols (352729)
- Method (283018)
- TOX (315459)
- P-CHEM (37872)
- ECOTOX (1197)
- EXPOSURE (120)

Figure 5: (a) The interface of NanoReg2 database containing “Nanomaterial type”, “Nanomaterial type”, “P-CHEM”, “TOX”, “ECOTOX” and “EXPOSURE” tabs on the left hand side to filter and access the database on (b) commercial names or (c) core materials of nanomaterials; parameters related to the nanomaterial's (d) physicochemistry; (e) toxicology; (f) eco-toxicology and (g) exposure

Table 3: Commercial nanomaterials for which experimental data can be accessed in NanoReg2 database

#	Manufacturer/ Supplier	Commercial name	Material	Pre-known Physicochemical properties (assay, if known)	Available at
1	PlasmaChem	P25	titanium dioxide nanoparticles	Specific surface area (BET); Avg. primary particle size; Tapped density; Moisture content (2 hours at 105 °C); Loss in ignition (TGA); pH in 4% dispersion; Elemental impurities (TGA); Sieve residue	http://www.plasmachem.com/shop/en/-type-p25/283-pl-tio-p25.html
2		PL-A-Fe ₃ O ₄	Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles	Avg. particle size (TEM); Zeta potential in 10 mM NaCl; Concentration	http://www.plasmachem.com/shop/en/-iron-iiii-oxide-fe3o4/94--pl-a-fe3o4-10ml.html
3		PL-M-Fe ₃ O ₄	Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles	Avg. particle size (TEM); Concentration	http://www.plasmachem.com/shop/en/-iron-iiii-oxide-fe3o4/93-pl-m-fe3o4-10ml.html
4	Mitsui-7 (termed as NRCWE-006 in the database)		MWCNT	Avg. primary size and shape (TEM & SEM); Elemental impurities	http://www.nano-device.eu/./NRCWE-006.pdf
5	Cheap Tubes (termed as NRCWE-007 in the database)		MWCNT	Avg. primary size and shape (TEM & SEM); Elemental impurities; Specific surface area	http://www.nano-device.eu/./NRCWE-007.pdf
6	Advancell Technologies	PLGA-PEO nanoparticles		Not available	-
7	Endorem	iron oxide nanoparticles		Not available	-
8	CM5050	Rhodamine B	fluorescent silicon dioxide nanoparticles	Not available	-
9	UPM	Birch hardwood Pulp	Not available	-	-
10	EU-JRC	JRCNM01000 (former EU-JRC code: NM-100)	titanium dioxide anatase pigment	Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS & TEM); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (VS); Crystallite size (XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM & DLS); Specific surface area (BET); Surface chemistry (TGA); Presence of organic coating (TGA and GC-MS on SOXHLET extracted compounds); Porosity (BET); Loss in ignition (TGA); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS); 24-hour solubility (24-h incubation in different cell media at 37° C and 5 % RH)	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/titanium-dioxide-nm-100-nm-101-nm-102-nm-103-nm-104-nm-105-characterisation-and-physico
11		JRCNM01001 (former EU-JRC code: NM-101)	titanium dioxide anatase nanoparticles	Agglomeration / aggregation (TEM); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Surface chemistry (TGA & XPS); Presence of organic coating (TGA and GC-MS on SOXHLET extracted compounds); Porosity (BET); Loss in ignition (TGA); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS); 24-hour solubility (24-h incubation in different cell media at 37° C and 5 % RH)	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/titanium-dioxide-nm-100-nm-101-nm-102-nm-103-nm-104-nm-105-characterisation-and-physico
12		JRCNM01002 (former EU-JRC code: NM-102)	titanium dioxide anatase nanoparticles	Homogeneity (DLS); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA & XPS); Presence of organic coating (TGA and GC-MS on SOXHLET extracted compounds); Porosity (BET); Loss in ignition (TGA); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS); 24-hour solubility (24-h incubation in different cell media at 37° C and 5 % RH)	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/titanium-dioxide-nm-100-nm-101-nm-102-nm-103-nm-104-nm-105-characterisation-and-physico

#	Manufacturer/ Supplier	Commercial name	Material	Pre-known Physicochemical properties (assay, if known)	Available at
13		JRCNM01003 (former EU-JRC code: NM-103)	titanium dioxide thermal, hydrophobic rutile nanoparticles	Homogeneity (DLS); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS, TEM & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM, AFM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA, DTA & XPS); Presence of organic coating (TGA and GC-MS on SOXHLET extracted compounds); Porosity (BET); Loss in ignition (TGA); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS); 24-hour solubility (24-h incubation in different cell media at 37° C and 5 % RH)	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/titanium-dioxide-nm-100-nm-101-nm-102-nm-103-nm-104-nm-105-characterisation-and-physico
14		JRCNM01004 (former EU-JRC code: NM-104)	titanium dioxide thermal, hydrophilic rutile nanoparticles	Homogeneity (DLS); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS, TEM & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM, AFM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA, DTA & XPS); Presence of organic coating (TGA and GC-MS on SOXHLET extracted compounds); Porosity (BET); Loss in ignition (TGA); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS); 24-hour solubility (24-h incubation in different cell media at 37° C and 5 % RH)	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/titanium-dioxide-nm-100-nm-101-nm-102-nm-103-nm-104-nm-105-characterisation-and-physico
15		JRCNM01005 (former EU-JRC code: NM-105)	titanium dioxide rutile-anatase nanoparticles	Homogeneity (DLS); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA, DTA & XPS); Presence of organic coating (TGA and GC-MS on SOXHLET extracted compounds); Porosity (BET); Loss in ignition (TGA); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS); 24-hour solubility (24-h incubation in different cell media at 37° C and 5 % RH)	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/titanium-dioxide-nm-100-nm-101-nm-102-nm-103-nm-104-nm-105-characterisation-and-physico
16		JRCNM01100 (former EU-JRC code: NM-110)	uncoated zinc oxide nanoparticles	Agglomeration / aggregation (SEM); Water Solubility/Dispersability (Colorimetric Test Kits); Crystalline phase (XRD); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Crystallite size (XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (DLS, TEM, SEM, disc centrifuge & SMPS); Homogeneity (SEM); Specific surface area (BET); Porosity (BJH); Surface chemistry (XPS); Loss in ignition (TGA); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES); Dispersion stability (turbidity meter); ; Zeta potential (zeta-potential standard); Redox Potential (ORP Tester); Photo-catalytic activity (UV-VIS spectroscopy);	http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC/64075/lana25066enn.pdf
17		JRCNM01101 (former EU-JRC code: NM-111)	triethoxycaprylsilane coated zinc oxide nanoparticles	Agglomeration / aggregation (SEM); Crystalline phase (XRD); Respirable dustiness (Miniaturized EN 15051 rotating drum); Crystallite size (XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (DLS, disc centrifuge, TEM & SEM); Homogeneity (SEM); Specific surface area (BET); Porosity (BJH); Surface chemistry (XPS); Loss in ignition (TGA); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES); Dispersion stability (turbidity meter);	
18		JRCNM0200	silicon dioxide nanoparticles	-	-
19		JRCNM02000 (former EU-JRC code: NM-200)	synthetic amorphous silicon dioxide nanoparticles PR-A-02	Homogeneity (DLS); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS, TEM & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (DISC CENTRIFUGE , TEM, AFM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS,	http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC/83506/lbna26046enn-nm_repository_sio2.pdf

#	Manufacturer/Supplier	Commercial name	Material	Pre-known Physicochemical properties (assay, if known)	Available at
				BET & TEM tomography); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA, DTA & XPS); Pour density (weighing); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS)	
20		JRCNM02001 (former EU-JRC code: NM-201)	synthetic amorphous silicon dioxide nanoparticles PR-B-01	Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS, TEM & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (DISC CENTRIFUGE , TEM, AFM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA & DTA); Pour density (weighing); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS)	
21		JRCNM02002 (former EU-JRC code: NM-202)	synthetic amorphous silicon dioxide nanoparticles PY-AB-03	Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS, TEM & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (DISC CENTRIFUGE , TEM, AFM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS & BET); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA & DTA); Pour density (weighing); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS)	
22		JRCNM02003 (former EU-JRC code: NM-203)	synthetic amorphous silicon dioxide nanoparticles PY-A-04	Homogeneity (DLS); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS, TEM & SAXS); Water solubility (SDR); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (SRD & VS); Crystallite size (SAXS & XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (DISC CENTRIFUGE , TEM, AFM & DLS); Specific surface area (SAXS, BET & TEM tomography); Zeta potential (Zetametry); Surface chemistry (TGA, DTA & XPS); Pour density (weighing); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (Benzoic acid probe to form hydroxyl-benzoic acid analyzed by HPLC-UV); Elemental analysis/impurities (Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS)	
23		JRCNM02102 (former EU-JRC code: NM-212)	cerium dioxide nanoparticles	Agglomeration/aggregation (DLS, DISC CENTRIFUGE , TEM & SEM); Water solubility (Flask method & Dialysis); Crystalline phase (XRD); Dustiness (RD); Crystallite size (XRD); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (CPS, TEM, SEM, SMPS & DLS); Specific surface area (BET); Zeta potential (LDE); Surface chemistry (XPS); Photocatalytic activity (UV-vis Spectroscopy); Pour density (weighing); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (ORP); OH radical formation (UV-vis Spectroscopy)	http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC/89825/lbna26649enn.pdf
24		JRCNM04000 (former EU-JRC code: NM-400)	MWCNT	Agglomeration/aggregation (TEM); Crystalline phase (XRD & Raman); Dustiness (VS); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM); Specific surface area (BET & SAXS); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (SDR); Elemental analysis/impurities (Quantitative ICP-MS & Semi-quantitative ICP-OES, ICP-MS & EDS) ; Presence of catalysts (TGA, DTA & XRD); Solubility in Gambles solution	
25		JRCNM04001 (former EU-JRC code: NM-401)	MWCNT	Agglomeration/aggregation (TEM); Crystalline phase (XRD & Raman); Dustiness (VS); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM); Specific surface area (BET & SAXS); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (SDR); Elemental analysis/impurities (Quantitative ICP-MS & Semi-quantitative ICP-OES & EDS) ; Presence of catalysts (TGA & DTA); Solubility in Gambles solution	http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC/91205/mwcnt-online.pdf
26		JRCNM04002 (former EU-JRC code: NM-402)	MWCNT	Agglomeration/aggregation (TEM); Crystalline phase (XRD & Raman); Dustiness (VS); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM); Specific surface area (BET & SAXS); Porosity (BET); Redox potential (SDR); OH radical formation (SDR); Elemental analysis/impurities (Quantitative ICP-MS & Semi-quantitative ICP-OES, ICP-MS & EDS) ; Presence of catalysts (TGA & XRD); Solubility in Gambles solution	

#	Manufacturer/Supplier	Commercial name	Material	Pre-known Physicochemical properties (assay, if known)	Available at
27		JRCNM04003(former EU-JRC code: NM-403)	MWCNT	Agglomeration/aggregation (TEM); Dustiness (VS); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM); Specific surface area (SAXS); Elemental analysis/impurities (Quantitative ICP-MS & Semi-quantitative ICP-OES); Presence of catalysts (TGA); Solubility in Gambles solution	
28		NM-220	barium sulfate nanoparticles	Not available	
29		NM-300K	silver nanoparticles	Homogeneity (ICP-OES); Agglomeration / aggregation (DLS & TEM); Water solubility (SDR); Representative TEM pictures (TEM); PSD (TEM, NTA, DLS & Zeta-sizer); Photo-catalytic activity (UV-VIS spectroscopy); Elemental analysis/impurities (ICP-OES)	https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/361f32fb-306f-46ed-98c3-6886e1934a53/language-en
30		NM-302	silver nanorods	Particle avg. size; Shape; Concentration	https://www.lqcstandards.com/.testing.pdf

Table 4: Core materials/substances for which experimental data can be accessed in NanoReg2 database

#	Core material/substance	Ontology ID	#	Core material/substance	Ontology ID
1	Cellulose nanofibers or nanofibrils	CHEBI:133349	14	60 µM H ₂ O ₂	CHEBI:16240
2	(1,4)-β-D-glucan	CHEBI:18246	15	Saline Bovine Serum Albumin solution	-
3	Barium Sulfate	CHEBI:133326	16	Cerium oxide	ENM:9000006
4	Nickel Ferrite	CHEBI:133333	17	Nanoclay	ENM:9000007
5	Zinc Ferrite	CHEBI:133337	18	Titanium oxide	NPO:1486
6	Nickel-Zinc Ferrite	CHEBI:133340	19	Zinc oxide	NPO:1542
7	Lipopolysaccharide	CHEBI:16412	20	Iron (II,III) oxide	NPO:1548
8	Calcium Carbonate	CHEBI:3341	21	Iron (III) oxide	NPO:1550
9	Graphite	CHEBI:33418	22	SWCNT	NPO:157
10	Silicon Dioxide	CHEBI:50828; NPO:1373	23	MWCNT	NPO:354
11	Polyacrylamide macromolecule	CHEBI:51135	24	Silver	NPO:1892
12	Mitomycin C	CHEBI:27504	25	Gold	NPO:401
13	Methyl methanesulfonate (MMS)	CHEBI:25255			

2.3.2.2 Parameter identification

Once the database is filtered for the nanomaterial (or type of nanomaterial) of interest, the second stage is the identification of the parameters in the database by a user. A user can find the parameter(s) of interest in Table 5 in which the parameters of 9 RA tools in SIA toolbox are enlisted. These tools are- CB Nanotool, Stoffenmanager (SM) nano, LICARA nanoScan, NanoRisk Cat, NanoSafer, FNN-BBN, Precautionary Matrix, GuideNano Tool and SUNDS. The parameters are further categorized in 5 classes: Physicochemical; Exposure; Environmental fate; Ecotoxicology and Human Toxicology.

Table 5: Parameters for RA tools in SIA toolbox with assays and steps to follow to retrieve data in NanoReg2 database

Parameter (ontology ID if available)	RA tools in SIA toolbox								Assay data points available in the database (ontology ID if available)	Assay relevant to be used for RA tools? (Y/N)	If relevant for RA tool, relevant for which type of material?	Steps to follow for data retrieval
	CB Nanotool	SM nano	LICARA NanoSCAN	NanoRisk Cat	Nano-Safer	FNN-BBN	Prec.Matrix	SUNDS				
Physicochemical												
Particle shape (NPO_274)	X	X	-	X	X	-	X	X	TEM (NPO_1430)	Yes	For e-beam insensitive and vacuum stable material; no insulators (for insulators thin metal layer/graphene layer needed)	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Aspect ratio shape/ Studies/ Aspect ratio shape/ TEM/ Morphology (OR shape)
									SEM (NPO_1429)	Yes		Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Aspect ratio shape/ Studies/ Aspect ratio shape/ SEM/ Morphology (OR shape)
Aspect ratio (ENM_8000064)	-	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	TEM (NPO_1430)	Yes		Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Aspect ratio shape/Studies/ Aspect ratio shape/Aspect ratio (in #)
Particle size (NPO_1694) or diameter (NPO_1539) or size distribution (NPO_1699)									DLS (NPO_1469)	No (Endpoint : Hydro-dynamic diameter)	-	-
									Differential Centrifugal Sedimentation (DCS)		-	-
									NTA		-	-
									SAXS (OBI_0002108)	Yes	For homogeneous amorphous and crystalline material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/ Studies/Particle size distribution/SAXS/ Size (in nm)
									WAXS	Yes	For homogeneous crystalline material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/ Studies/WAXS/Core size (in nm)
									TEM (NPO_1430)	Yes	For e-beam insensitive and vacuum stable material; no insulators (for insulators thin metal layer/graphene layer needed)	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/Studies/TEM/Particle size (in nm)
									SEM (NPO_1429)	Yes		Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/Studies /SEM/ Particle size (in nm)
Water solubility (NPO_500)	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	ICP-MS (CHMO_0000538)	Yes	For metal elements	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Water solubility/ Studies/ICP-MS/ Element dissolution concentration (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb)

Parameter (ontology ID if available)	RA tools in SIA toolbox								Assay data points available in the database (ontology ID if available)	Assay relevant to be used for RA tools? (Y/N)	If relevant for RA tool, relevant for which type of material?	Steps to follow for data retrieval
	CB Nanotool	SM nano	LICARA NanosCAN	NanoRisk Cat	Nano-Safer	FNN-BBN	Prec.Matrix	SUNDS				
									sp-ICP-MS	Yes		Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Water solubility/ Studies/sp-ICP-MS/ Element dissolution concentration (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb)
									ICP-OES	Yes		Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Water solubility/ Studies/ICP-OES/ Element dissolution concentration (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb)
Dustiness (ENM_0000085)	X	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	Vortex shaker (ENM_8000253)	Yes	For powder	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Dustiness/Studies/Respirable dustiness index (in mg/kg)
Particle concentration (NPO_1830)	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	TGA (CHMO_0000690)	Yes	For heat sensitive material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Stability thermal/ Studies/TGA/Mass loss % (in wt%)
									sp-ICP-MS	Yes	For metal elements	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/ Studies/sp-ICP-MS/ Concentration (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%)
Aggregation/ Agglomeration (NPO_1966)	-	-	X	X	-	-	X	-	SEM (NPO_1429)	Yes	For e-beam insensitive and vacuum stable material; no insulators (for insulators thin metal layer/ graphene layer needed)	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Agglomeration Aggregation state/ Studies/Agglomeration Aggregation state
									DLS (NPO_1469)	Yes	For monodisperse samples and the samples that do not indicate fluorescence in the wavelength of the laser	Nanomaterial (or type)/P_CHEM/Particle size distribution/Studies/Particle size distribution/DLS/Hydrodynamic diameter (in nm)
									Zeta potential (using electrophoretic light scattering)	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ zeta potential/ Studies /zeta potential (in mV)
									Centrifugal Liquid Segmentation (CLS)	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P_CHEM/Particle size distribution/Studies/Particle size distribution/CLS/PDI (in #)
Specific Surface area (CHEMINF_000247)	X	-	X	-	X	-	X	X	BET	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Specific surface area /Studies/BET/SSA (in m ² /g)
									SAXS (OBI_0002108)	Yes	For homogeneous amorphous and crystalline material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Specific surface area /Studies/SAXS/SSA (in m ² /g)
Density	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	He-Pycno metry	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/PC Density Section/ Studies/He-

Parameter (ontology ID if available)	RA tools in SIA toolbox								Assay data points available in the database (ontology ID if available)	Assay relevant to be used for RA tools? (Y/N)	If relevant for RA tool, relevant for which type of material?	Steps to follow for data retrieval
	CB Nanotool	SM nano	LICARA NanosCAN	NanoRisk Cat	Nano-Safer	FNN-BBN	Prec-Matrix	SUNDS				
											Pycnometer/Density (in g/cm ³)	
									Differential Centrifugal Sedimentation (DCS)	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/PC Density Section/Studies/DCS/Density (in g/cm ³)
									sp-ICP-MS	Yes	For metal elements	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/PC Density Section/Studies/sp-ICP-MS/Density (in g/cm ³)
Chemical composition including impurities (ENM_0000082)									CHN analysis (ENM_8000256)	Yes	For thermally conducting material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/CHN analysis (in %)
									Colorimetry	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/Studies/Colorimetry/Metal ion concentration (in µg/ml)
									XPS (NPO_1471)	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/Studies/XPS/ Elemental weight %
			X	X			X		ICP-MS (CHMO_0000538)	Yes	For the detection of metal elements and organic molecules e.g. polymers, dendrimers etc.	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/Studies/ICP-MS (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%) OR Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Impurities/Studies/ICP-MS (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%) OR Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/Studies/Surface chemistry/ICP-MS (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%)
									ICP-OES	Yes		Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/Studies/ICP-MS (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%) OR Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Impurities/Studies/ICP-MS (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%) OR Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/Studies/Surface chemistry/ICP-OES (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%)
									HPLC-MS	Yes	Not applicable for thermally labile material that exhibit high polarity	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/Studies/Surface chemistry/HPLC-MS (in ppm)

Parameter (ontology ID if available)	RA tools in SIA toolbox								Assay data points available in the database (ontology ID if available)	Assay relevant to be used for RA tools? (Y/N)	If relevant for RA tool, relevant for which type of material?	Steps to follow for data retrieval	
	CB Nanotool	SM nano	LICARA NanosCAN	NanoRisk Cat	Nano-Safer	FNN-BBN	Prec.Matrix	SUNDS					
										EDS	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Impurities/Studies/Impurities/EDS (in wt%)
										EDX	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/Surface chemistry/EDX (in wt%)
										HAADF-STEM	Yes	For e-beam insensitive material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/Surface chemistry/HAADF-STEM (in wt%)
										TGA	Yes	For heat sensitive material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Stability thermal/ Studies/TGA/Mass loss % (in wt%)
										ATR-FTIR	Yes	For material with dipole moment in its molecules and wavenumber range from 4000 to 500	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/Surface chemistry/ATR-FTIR/Functional group
Chemical composition of released material	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-		ICP-MS (CHMO_0000538)	Yes	For metal elements	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/Studies/ICP-MS (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb or wt%)
Surface coating (NPO_1962)	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	X		TGA	Yes	For heat sensitive material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Stability thermal/ Studies/TGA/Mass loss % (in wt%)
										HPLC-MS (CHMO_0000543)	Yes	Not applicable for thermally labile material that exhibits high polarity	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/Surface chemistry/HPLC-MS (in ppm)
										CHN analysis (ENM_8000256)	Yes	For thermally conducting material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/CHN analysis/Element Weight % (in %)
										HAADF-STEM	Yes	For e-beam insensitive material	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/Surface chemistry/HAADF-STEM (in wt%)
										ATR-FTIR	Yes	For material with dipole moment in its molecules and wavenumber range from 4000 to 500	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Surface chemistry/ Studies/Surface chemistry/ATR-FTIR/Functional group
										XPS (NPO_1471)	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Physchem other/ Studies/XPS/Elemental weight %
Rigidity	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-		-	-	-	-

Parameter (ontology ID if available)	RA tools in SIA toolbox								Assay data points available in the database (ontology ID if available)	Assay relevant to be used for RA tools? (Y/N)	If relevant for RA tool, relevant for which type of material?	Steps to follow for data retrieval
	CB Nanotool	SM nano	LICARA NanoSCAN	NanoRisk Cat	Nano-Safer	FNN-BBN	Prec.Matrix	SUNDS				
Medium surrounding the nanomaterial upon release	-	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	-	-		-
Exposure												
Engineering control or ventilation	X	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	-	-	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/Exposure/Personal worker exposure/Studies/Protocol/ General ventilation OR Local control
Activity level in the working room	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
Amount of material used (in one task or day, month or year)	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	-	-
Number of employees with the same exposure	X	X	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Operation or task frequency	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	-	-
Operation or task duration	X	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
Size (or volume) of the working room	-	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
Hygiene of the living room	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Inspections (or maintenance) of machines/ancillary equipment	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Distance between source and worker	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Process or source energy level	-	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
Physical enclosure(s)	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Nanomaterial (or type)/Exposure/Personal worker exposure/Studies/Protocol/Segregation
Size of the consumer population	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Amount of material handled by a consumer (in one day)	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Consumer handling frequency of the material	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Std. Process Categories (PROCs)	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Nanomaterial (or type)/Exposure/Personal worker exposure/Studies/Protocol/Activity type
Std. Environmental Release Categories (ERCs)	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Parameter (ontology ID if available)	RA tools in SIA toolbox								Assay data points available in the database (ontology ID if available)	Assay relevant to be used for RA tools? (Y/N)	If relevant for RA tool, relevant for which type of material?	Steps to follow for data retrieval
	CB Nanotool	SM nano	LICARA NanosCAN	NanoRisk Cat	Nano-Safer	FNN-BBN	Prec-Matrix	SUNDS				
Environmental fate												
Stability or half-life in physiological matrix/environmental conditions	-	-	X	X	-	-	X	-	ICP-MS (CHMO_0000538)	Yes	For metal elements	Nanomaterial (or type)/P-CHEM/ Water solubility/ Dissolution time/ Studies/Water solubility/ Protocol/(Total) Dissolution time (in min or h)
									sp-ICP-MS	Yes		
										ICP-OES		
Dispersion stability in water	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Deagglomeration in water, soil or sediment	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Bioaccumulation potential or Bioconcentration factor (BCF)	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Environmental toxicology												
Short or long term effects on sediment species (ENM_0000009)	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	NOEC MAR	Yes	All	Nanomaterial (or type)/ ECOTOX/Sediment Toxicity/Studies/ECOTOX/ Sediment Toxicity
									LOEC MAR			
Short or long term effects on soil species (ENM_0000008)	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	NOEC MAR	Yes	All	Nanomaterial (or type)/ ECOTOX/ Toxicity to soil macro organisms/ Studies/ ECOTOX/Toxicity to soil macro organisms
									LOEC MAR			
									NOEC MAR			Nanomaterial (or type)/ ECOTOX/Toxicity to soil microorganisms/ Studies/ ECOTOX/Toxicity to soil microorganisms
									LOEC MAR			
Short or long term effect on terrestrial species (ENM_0000014)	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	NOEC MAR	Yes	All	Nanomaterial (or type)/ ECOTOX/Toxicity to terrestrial plants/Studies/ ECOTOX/Toxicity to terrestrial plants
Short (ENM_0000010) or long term (ENM_0000011) effect on aquatic vertebrates	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	LC10	Yes	All	Nanomaterial (or type)/ ECOTOX/ Short-term toxicity to fish/Studies/ ECOTOX/Short-term toxicity to fish
									LC50			
									EC10			
									EC20			
									EC50			
									NOEC			
Short or long term effect on aquatic invertebrate(ENM_0000006)	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	LC10	Yes	All	Nanomaterial (or type)/ ECOTOX/Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates/Studies/ ECOTOX/ Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates
									LC50			
									EC10			
									EC20			
									EC50			
									NOEC			
								LOEC				
Toxicology												
Oral Toxicity (ENM_0000019)	-	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	Genotoxicity	Yes (but only to limited extent, since only a limited amount of endpoints are currently included)	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/Repeated dose toxicity-oral/Studies/TOX/repeated dose toxicity-oral/OECD guideline 408/ DNA strand breaks (in %) OR frequency of micronucleated reticulocytes OR

									Neutral Red OR NRU			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Barrier integrity/NRU/percentage viability (in %)
									RN			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/RN/max cytotox (in %)
									Flow cytometry with PI staining			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Flow cytometry with PI staining/max concentration (in %)
									Barrier integrity (Lucifer Yellow, TEER, trypan blue, Impedance adherent cell)			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Barrier integrity/trypan blue/max cytotoxicity (in %)
									Colony forming			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Barrier integrity/Colony forming/ number of colonies (in #) or CFE (in %)
									Cell counts/relative increase in cell counts			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/cell count or RICC/min cytotoxicity (in %) or max cytotoxicity (in %) or first toxic dose (in ug/cm3)
Skin irritation (ENM_0000032) /eye irritation (ENM_0000033)	-	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Radical formation	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	-	Electronic spin resonance (ESR)	Yes	all	Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Oxidative stress/Electronic spin resonance ERS/surface reactivity (CPH/DH2O) or surface reactivity (DMPO/DH2O) (in #)
									H2DFCDA			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Oxidative stress/H2DFCDA/percentage of control (in %)
									HE oxidation			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/oxidative stress/DHEfacs or 3T3-ROS-NM/HE positive cells(%of control) or HE positive cells (average raw data) (in %) or %response-cytotox-ROS or average raw data-cytotox-ROS (In mg/mL)
									DCFDA			Nanomaterial (or type)/TOX/immunotoxicity/Studies/TOX/Oxidative stress/DCFDA/Fluorescence fold increase vs control or fluorescence (in ug/cm2)
OEL	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
DNEL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
NOEC (ENM_0000056)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
NOAEL (ENM_0000057)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-

EC10 (BAO_0001263)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
PNEC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Benchmark dose (BMD) or response (BMR)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Study type (Chronic, sub-chronic, sub-acute, repro/develop)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Test species (rat/mouse)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Species weight	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Human weight (EFO_0004338)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Population Incidence Goal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
Interspecies toxicokinetic/toxicodynamic differences	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-

2.3.2.3 Relevant assay identification

After the user has refined the database to his/her nanomaterial and parameter(s) of interest, the next step is to select the data corresponding to the selected nanomaterial and parameter. In NanoReg2 database, there can be multiple assays to determine a single parameter. For example, for the parameter “Particle size”, the data points of DLS, DCS, NTA, SAXS, WAXS, TEM and SEM assays are available (Table 5). However, it is not necessary that all these assays provide data which are suitable for the user. The DLS, DCS and NTA analyze a colloidal suspension. Therefore, the particle size provided by these assays corresponds to hydrodynamic size of particle agglomerates or aggregates. The particle size, asked in the SIA tools, corresponds to a diameter of the sphere that has the same surface area as a given particle in free, bound, agglomerated or aggregated state, i.e. a surface equivalent diameter of the particle. This implies that the suitable assays providing “tool relevant” data on the particle size are SAXS, WAXS, TEM and SEM. Furthermore, if the product to test is a polymer with low molecular mass, then it might deteriorate when subjected to e-beam in SEM and TEM assays. Moreover, WAXS is only relevant for crystalline materials. This further implies that the “tool relevant” SEM and TEM assays are not relevant for e-beam sensitive products. Similarly, “tool relevant” WAXS assay is not relevant for amorphous products. Thus, a user should retrieve the data of an assay which is both tool and product relevant (Figure 4). These two refining criteria are also shown in Table 5.

2.3.2.4 Data retrieval

The necessary steps to retrieve the data of an assay from NanoReg2 database are shown in the last column of Table 6. It summarizes the successive steps (described in sections 3.2.1, 3.2.2 and 3.2.3) for the data retrieval. These steps follow a similar information path for all parameters, as shown in Figure 1. For example, Table 6 shows the following steps to take to retrieve the data for the parameter “Water solubility” which is obtained using a “sp-ICP-MS” assay.

Nanomaterial (or type) / P-CHEM / Water solubility / Studies / Water solubility / sp-ICP-MS /
 Step 1 Step 2 Step 3 Step 4 Step 5 Step 6
Element dissolution concentration (in mg/ml or ppm or ppb)
 Step 7

The filter referring to the “nanomaterial” or its “type” must be selected first (step 1). The nanomaterial of interest can either be absent or available in the database. In the former case, the user can refer to the grouping approach in which another nanomaterial can be selected from the NanoReg2 database whose physicochemical and human health and/or ecotoxicological properties and/or environmental fate properties are likely to be similar or follow a regular pattern, usually as a result of structural similarity to the nanomaterial of interest. The user can also refer to the read-across approach which involves the identification of another nanomaterial or mode or mechanism of action that is common to the nanomaterial of interest. It also involves the assumption that the known value of a property for one nanomaterial can be used to estimate the unknown value of the same property for the nanomaterial of

interest. However, for both grouping and read-across approaches, expert judgement is needed. If both of the approaches are not possible, the user should exit the database. In the latter case where the nanomaterial of interest is available in the database, the user should proceed to step 2 by selecting the filter for the parameter category (“P-CHEM” in the present case) and clicking on it.

This opens the parameter category tab and shows all available parameters corresponding to the selected nanomaterial and for which the data is present in the database. In step 3, consequently, the parameter of interest (“Water solubility” in the present case) filter is selected. For user reference, the three selected filters also appear on the top of the list of the filtered studies. Clicking “Studies” in step 4 for any one of the filtered studies opens all the data available in the selected study in a new tab. The user can scroll down the page to find the parameter of interest in step 5. A list of results are shown, corresponding to different assays used to determine the parameter of interest. The user can select a tool and product relevant assay in step 6 (“sp-ICP-MS” in the present case), according to the guidelines in Table 6. Finally, in the step 7 and for present case, the data on the parameter of interest is expressed as “Element dissolution concentration” in “mg/ml” or “µg/ml” or “ppm” or “ppb”.

It should be noted that filtering of the database (steps 1-3) may result in plural studies. Although these studies correspond to the same selected nanomaterial and parameter, they can contain data from different assays or one assay performed using different protocols or experimental conditions. Therefore, care about the experimental conditions must be taken in which the assay is performed. The user can scan through the protocol in the same column as that of the assay, as shown in Figure 6.

Reference	Protocol	Endpoint	Result	Result	replicate	Provided by
spICPMS_TI_0.5_1 (2014)	sp_ICP-MS .Instrument settings/ Isotope dwell time: 3 millisecond .Instrument settings/ Nebulization efficiency: 2.4 % .Instrument settings/ Sample inject flow: 0.5 ml/min .Instrument settings/ Total acquisition time: 1 minute T.Method: spICPMS TI .Reference material/ Concentration: 50 g/cm ⁻³ .Reference material/ Manufacturer: NIST .Reference material/ Mean reference particle density: 19.3 g/ml .Reference material/ Mean reference particle diameter: 60 nm .Reference material/ Product number: 8013 T.Reference material/ Reference element mass: 197 amu .Respons factor calibration/ Respons at element amu: 15322 cps/ppb T.sp_ICP-MS/ Instrument model: X series 2 ICP-MS T.sp_ICP-MS/ Instrument model manufacturer: Thermo scientific Dispersion protocol: sp_ICP-MS TI Vial: 07789	Ti	0.29 µg/ml	-	0	DLO-RIKILT
525a511-8fd8-a797-0d0c-4747		Ti.nebulization efficiency	2.4 %	-	-	

Figure 6: An example showing the experimental protocol using which a sp-ICP-MS assay is performed to determine the water solubility of JRCNM01001a

2.4 Considerations regarding input parameters

In the present deliverable, detailed information on the input parameters of the SIA supporting tools is provided. These input parameters are then mapped against the availability of their corresponding data in NanoReg2 and NECID databases. Thanks to a fit-gap analysis, the input parameter classes are indicated which find lack of data in these databases. This analysis can serve as a pivot point to further enrich the databases. For the classes which have their data available, a user can easily retrieve the data using the user guidance. This guidance contains a step-by-step procedure for data retrieval. In addition, it helps the user to determine the assays which are both tool and product relevant and can be used for the input parameters. However, there are some considerations regarding certain input

parameters which are worth discussing, and which may be valuable for users and database developers to be aware of. They are discussed in the sections 2.4.1, 2.4.2 and 2.4.3.

2.4.1 *Environmental fate related input parameters*

2.4.1.1 *Stability or half-life in physiological matrix/environmental conditions*

LICARA NanoScan scores potential environmental risks of a nanomaterial with a relative ranking value between 0 and 1. In order to draw this score, the tool asks the user to indicate stability of the nanomaterial in the environment with a half-life expressed as 'hours, days-weeks, months, or unknown'. The underlying rationale is that unstable nanomaterials are most rapidly removed, so that exposure and consequential risks for the organisms living in the environment are relatively low. The rates at which nanomaterials are removed often depend on multiple environmental fate processes e.g. dissolution, oxidation, sulphidation and biodegradation. Moreover, it is often a complex exercise to quantify the rates for such fate processes as they depend on the intrinsic physicochemical properties of the nanomaterial itself - e.g size, shape, chemical composition,- as well as environmental conditions such as pH, ionic strength and the presence of natural organic matter (Quik et al., 2011).

The NanoReg2 database does not include filters to directly collect data that refers to the environmental stability of nanomaterials, but the database can be used to obtain such data nonetheless. One of the most important fate processes responsible for the removal of inorganic nanomaterials from the environment is dissolution (Hjorth et al., 2017). The process of dissolution is often expressed with a rate, time, or half-life as a description of the test conditions performed to determine the solubility of a nanomaterial. 'Solubility' is included as a filter in the NanoReg2 database and can be used to obtain a dissolution half-life accurate enough for LICARA NanoScan. The tool only asks for an indication of stability half-life as 'hours, days-weeks, months or unknown', so that a rough interpretation of the dissolution of the nanomaterial is already sufficient.

The first step to collect such data from the NanoReg2 database is to check whether the nanomaterial is soluble. To do so, the filter referring to the 'nanomaterial' must be selected first. Then the filter 'water solubility' is to be selected that is under the tab 'P-CHEM'. In case this filter is not present under the tab, the user can conservatively choose the option 'unknown' to express the stability half-life in LICARA NanoScan. After selecting the 'water solubility' filter the user is referred to the conditions of the solubility experiment, which can be accessed by following the 'studies' link that is under the tab 'SELECTION'. A new window will open which gives a small overview table of the nanomaterial and studies considered. Click the link under 'substance name' and open the 'WATER SOLUBILITY' tab in the new window. Then scan through the column called 'protocol' in order to check whether experimental conditions are described referring to 'dissolution time'. If such information is not present, then select the 'Unknown' stability half-life in the LICARA NanoScan. However, if information 'dissolution time' is present, it is nonetheless necessary to check whether the experimental conditions are suitable to reflect realistic environmental conditions, i.e. pH should be within the range of 5-9, temperature 10-40°C, the liquid medium should be water, and ionic strength should be within the range of 1-1000 mM (Hjorth et al., 2017). In case experimental conditions do not agree with these terms, the 'Unknown' stability half-life should be selected in LICARA NanoScan as it is still 'unknown' to what extent the nanomaterial dissolves under realistic environmental conditions.

In case the environmental conditions agree with the terms, then conservatively choose the value that refers to the lowest rate of dissolution, i.e. highest dissolution time, half-life or lowest rate. Then interpret the order of magnitude of the given dissolution time to reflect "hours, days-week or months", or "unknown" if dissolution time is greater than one year. The interpreted dissolution times can then be used as an indication for environmental stability half-life in LICARA NanoScan.

2.4.1.2 *Bioaccumulation potential or Bioconcentration factor (BCF)*

The bioconcentration factor (BCF) is used in chemical safety assessment to indicate the extent to which a chemical is able to reside in organisms and accumulate in the food chain. The BCF is defined as the ratio of the concentration of a substance in an organism (g/ kg bw) to the concentration in water (g/L)

once a (Skjolding, 2015) steady state has been achieved. In NanoRiskCat a cutoff value of 50 is recommended as an indication for possible environmental risks of nanomaterial due to bioaccumulation in the food chain.

However, a BCF for nanomaterials cannot be calculated with the same approach as for dissolved chemicals. The BCF for dissolved chemicals is calculated from the thermodynamic equilibrium (Rasmussen et al., 2016) reached between the organism and the surrounding water (Cornelis, 2015). Such thermodynamic equilibrium is not reached for nanomaterials, so that passive diffusion from the organisms back to the surrounding water is not expected (Kuehnelt and Nickel, 2014). The BCF for nanomaterials should therefore be derived experimentally from dietary uptake and depuration rates. Such experimental data is scarce and not included in the NanoReg2 database. However a BCF study is applicable via the aqueous route for organic nanomaterials that are water soluble and/or would have a high dissolution rate (ECHA, 2017). The NanoReg2 database can be consulted to check whether the nanomaterial of interest meets these terms. If so, the BCF derived for the dissolved chemical equivalent of the nanomaterial may be of use. In case the nanomaterial does not meet these terms it is recommended to employ a BCF greater than 50 in NanoRiskCat, because that is (i) most conservative as high potential risk of bioaccumulation is related to a high BCF and (ii) most plausible as insoluble inorganic nanomaterials are not expected to passively diffuse out of the organism back to the surrounding water.

To first step to consult the NanoReg2 database in order to check whether the nanomaterial is organic, soluble and dissolves rapidly is to select the nanomaterial of interest under the tab 'NANOMATERIAL'. Then open the tab 'P-CHEM' and click 'Water solubility'. In case the filter leads to zero search results in the hit list, the nanomaterial can be considered to be insoluble. A BCF greater than 50 should then be filled in NanoRiskCat. If the search does show hits for 'water solubility' it can be checked whether the nanomaterial is organic. To do so, click 'material' and check whether the chemical composition of the nanomaterial contains the element of carbon. In the case the material does not include carbon, it is inorganic. A BCF greater than 50 should then be filled in NanoRiskCat. In case the material is both organic and soluble it can be checked whether it also dissolves rapidly. Guidance in experimentally determining BCFs refer to a settling-in period of 48 hours (OECD, 2012). The nanomaterial should thus be dissolved (completely) within 48 hours in order to use the BCF of the dissolved equivalent. This can be checked in the NanoReg2 database by clicking the 'studies' link of the hit. A new window will open and click on the tab 'P-CHEM' tab and open 'Water solubility'. Scroll through the column 'protocol' and check whether dissolution times are within 48 hours. If this is the case, the BCF of the dissolved equivalent of the nanomaterial can be inserted in NanoRiskCat. If this is not the case, it is recommended to indicate that BCF is greater than 50.

2.4.1.3 *Dispersion stability and deagglomeration in water, soil or sediment*

The user of NanoRiskCat is encouraged to draw a written evaluation aimed at answering whether the nanomaterial is novel, poses ecosystem effects or is novel "yes", "maybe", "no" or "no data". The NanoReg2 database does not include such data and is thus not applicable for this evaluation, except for nanomaterials for which it is indicated earlier in the NanoRiskCat tool that the dissolved chemical equivalent can be considered (to derive the BCF). In that case the material is not "novel" and the long range transport and potential for ecosystems effects can be predicted based on the knowledge of the dissolved chemical equivalent.

2.4.2 *Ecotoxicology related input parameters*

The 'ECOTOX' filters prescribed in the guidance table lead to a summary of the ecotoxicological endpoints available for the earlier selected nanomaterial. However, it is directly which type of specific endpoints are available in the database until is linked to the 'Studies' window and opens the results under the 'EcoTox' menu. It is also possible to check for the availability of a specific endpoint and to apply filter for it under the tab 'Protocols'. However, this search assignment requires some knowledge about the protocols of the short-term ecotoxicological tests included in the NanoReg2 database with respect to the type of the studied effect, the determined thresholds, test conditions, exposed organism and test media representing environmental compartments such as fresh water, soil and sediments.

Therefore, it is recommended to add a search pattern that considers the 'Protocol' filters, to explain the underlying data of the 'ECOTOX' and 'Protocol' filters and how these data are linked to each other in

the database (Table 6). As such, it is also recommendable to briefly explain the ecotoxicology terminology, so that database users that are unfamiliar in the field of ecotoxicology easily find the desired ecotoxicology data points nonetheless.

The NanoReg2 database includes experimental study results of ecotoxicology tests determining thresholds for different nanomaterials, different ecotoxicological effects, different organisms and different. In order to collect the desired ecotoxicological data from the NanoReg2 database first select the nanomaterial of interest under the tab 'nanomaterial'. Then open the tab 'ECOTOX' and check whether ecotoxicology data is available in the database at all. At this point the user can choose the most appropriate test protocol or ECOTOX filter with respect to the ecotoxicological endpoint, exposed organism (assay) and environmental compartment (Table 6). After selecting the appropriate 'ECOTOX' or 'PROTOCOL' filter, click the link called 'studies'. A new window will open. Unfold the 'ECOTOX' tab in this window. Unfold the summary data menu and collect the ecotoxicological data of interest.

Table 6: NanoReg2 Protocol and ECOTOX database filters and underlying data; ECx: Concentration at which 'x' percent of the exposed organisms suffer from the ecotoxicological effect; LCx: Lethal concentration at which 'x' percent of the exposed organisms suffer from mortality; NOEC: No observed effect concentration; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration

NanoReg2 Protocol Filter	NanoReg2 ECOTOX filter	Assay(s)	Environmental compartment	Ecotoxicological effect(s)	Endpoint(s)	Ref
NanoReg D4.12	Toxicity to soil macroorganisms	C. Elegans	Soil	Growth, fertility, and reproduction inhibition	ECx	Mendoza & Cerillo, 2016
OECD TG 201	Toxicity to aquatic algae and cyanobacteria	Freshwater Algae and Cyanobacteria	Water	Growth inhibition	ECx, LOEC, NOEC	OECD 2011
OECD TG 202	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	Daphnia	Water	Immobilization or any other adverse effects	EC 50	OECD, 2004
OECD TG 210	Short-term toxicity to fish	Fish	Water	Lethal and sub-lethal	LCx, ECx	OECD, 2013
OECD TG 216	Toxicity to soil microorganisms	Soil microorganisms	Soil	Nitrogen transformation	ECx	OECD, 2000a
OECD TG 217	Toxicity to soil microorganisms	Soil microorganisms	Soil	Carbon transformation	ECx	OECD, 2000b
OECD TG 225	Sediment toxicity	Sea urchin	Sediment	Juvenile growth	ECx, LOEC, NOEC	OECD, 2000c
Plant root length elongation	Toxicity to terrestrial plants	L. Sativa	Soil	Root growth	LOEC, NOEC	-
PLHC Fish cell line	Short-term toxicity to fish	Fish	Water	Cytotoxicity	ECx	-
SOP Toxicity	Toxicity to soil macroorganisms	C. Elegans	Soil	Growth, fertility, and reproduction inhibition		Jensen et al., 2015
SOP Toxicity	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	Daphnia magna	Water without NOM	Immobilization or any other adverse effects	ECx	Jensen et al., 2015
SOP Toxicity	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	Daphnia magna	Water with NOM	Immobilization or any other adverse effects	ECx	Jensen et al., 2015
SOP Toxicity	Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates	Fish	Water	Lethal and sub-lethal	LCx	Jensen et al., 2015
SOP Toxicity	Toxicity to aquatic algae and cyanobacteria	Microalgae	Water without NOM	Growth inhibition	LCx	Jensen et al., 2015
SOP Toxicity	Toxicity to aquatic algae and cyanobacteria	Microalgae	Water with NOM	Growth inhibition	LCx	Jensen et al., 2015

2.4.3 *Human toxicology related input parameters*

The data corresponding to the parameters like “OELs”, “DNELs”, “NOAELs”, “BMD” or other points of departure for human risk assessment are not included in the database, since no interpreted study results are included, only data on separate endpoints. The other parameters including “Study type”, “Test species” and “Species weight” are although included in the database, they can only be used if in combination with aforementioned point of departure. Moreover, the data retrieval path for “Cytotoxicity” is shown for different cell lines, including MH-S, Calu-3, RAW 264.7, NIH3T3, TM3, HMDM, Caco-2 and mES cells. The 8 tools included in the user guidance have different ways of presenting the toxicology data. Consequently, in every case, data obtained from the database must be transformed into specific criteria defined by each tool.

For instance, CB Nanotool needs the data to be transformed to “Tox” or “No Tox”; NanoSafer needs R- and H-phrases for the risk assessment; LICARA NanoSCAN and Swiss Precautionary Matrix give the results as “low”, “medium” or “high”; NanoRiskCat gives colour coded results; SUNDS needs data as “NOAEL” and benchmark dose must be introduced into the tool. Furthermore, the means for interpreting and scoring different types of human toxicity data, e.g. for ranking and prioritization useful in decision taking during SbD strategies, are being developed and implemented for use in conjunction with the risk assessment tools presented here (i.e. the SIA tools) within NanoReg2 WP1 (D1.7) and other European projects such as caLIBRAte (D2.4).

2.5 Conclusions

Within Task 3.2, the NanoReg2 database structure has been developed so that it supports the SIA. The database structure has been based on the FP7 eNanoMapper project database and its needs (in the context of WP3) are dependent on the specific tools which are selected to support the SIA. The input parameters for these tools form the basis for the database structure. Within the NanoReg2 project, it has been concluded that a coordinating Database Solution Team was needed in order to harmonize database activities within NanoReg2. This team consists of NanoReg2 partners with data management and database experience. The objective of the solution team is to find solutions for all database and data management issues in the NanoReg2 project, in particular those which relate to WPs 1 and 3, but also involve WPs 2 and 4.

The present deliverable provides a guidance to support users of the SIA toolbox in finding relevant input data in the NanoReg2 database. For this, a link was made with the eNanoMapper ontology and the databases of NanoReg2 and NECID. As shown in Annex 3, the complexity level of the linking was decided to be kept at level two which provides the information on actual assays that are relevant for the specific input parameter from the NanoReg2 database and matches with the exact meaning of the parameter in the tool.

Using a fit-gap analysis, gaps in the database, based on tool input parameters, have been identified. The parameter classes for which no data is available in the database are, namely, Product application & conditions, Consumer Exposure, NM emission to the environment, Functionality, Nano-enabled product physico-chemical properties and Market & societal benefits. A concept of integration of functionality aspects has, nevertheless, been provided by INM within the work done in T3.2.

A user guidance has been developed as a part of this deliverable that provides step-by-step illustrative guidance through the data retrieval process in the NanoReg2 database for the risk assessment (RA) of a product. In addition, it assists the user in deciding the most relevant assay for both the particular parameter and the product being assessed. The output of this deliverable strongly connects to D3.3 (Safe innovations guidance manual for decision per gate) and D4.6 (Industrial SbD tools and SbD SOPs for the industrial nanotechnology community). The guidance described in the deliverable will be published online to support the SIA Toolbox.

3 Deviations from the work plan

With the formation of the database solution team all database and data management activities within the NanoReg2 project are coordinated by the database solution team. Therefore the actual building of the database structure and ontology, as described in D3.2, was not carried out by the T3.2 partners. The relevant parameters description and link to the SIA toolbox and functionality were developed by the T3.2 partners.

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5 List of abbreviations

EC	European Commission
FP 7	7 th Framework Programme, EU Research funding 2007 - 2013
H2020	Horizon 2020, The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
IOM	Institute of Occupational Medicine
ISA-TAB	Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) tab-delimited (TAB)
KI	Karolinska Institutet
NEB	NanoReg2 Executive Board
SAR	Structure activity Relationship
SbD	Safe by Design
SIA	Safe Innovation Approach
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TNO	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepaste Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek
WP	Work Package

6 Annexes

Annex 1. Overview of Database needs for WPs 1 to 4

Development and implementation of Grouping and Safe-by-Design approaches within regulatory frameworks

Overview of Database needs for WPs 1 to 4

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2. Data Sources
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Introduction

The aim of this review is to compile the data requirements and wishes of the four WPs in NanoReg2 which will generate and use new and existing data to achieve their deliverables. Each WP has its own needs and requirements, but the overall aim is to include everything in one project database, which will be modelled around eNanoMapper. Partner Idea Consult who is one of the main partners in eNanoMapper is also a partner in NanoReg2 and will therefore be responsible for setting up a functioning database, using the criteria identified below.

For WP1, we will use the NanoReg2 database to develop NM grouping

For WP2, the NanoReg2 database will collect all information required to perform RA coupled with LCA and socio/economic assessment.

For WP3, the purpose of the database is to support the Safe by Design approach. The SbD approach aims at integrating safety and functionality aspects at all stages of the innovation process. In general, WP3 needs the following aspects to be included in the database: physical-chemical characterization, functionality data, and hazard and exposure data.

For WP4, the objective is to demonstrate the integration of the SbD approaches to the innovation process of the industrial partners, and we will use existing data as well as generate new data which are necessary for WP2 to carry out the risk assessment (exposure, hazard, phys-chem) and demonstrate the effectiveness of SbD as well as underlying strategies (grouping of ENMs). It is not certain that all new data generated will be available for inclusion in the database, as this will depend on agreement of the industrial case study provider.

Inventory of the purpose of the NanoReg2 database

First of all, an inventory is needed to establish the purpose of the NanoReg2 database, i.e. what users (NanoReg2 partners) will do with the NanoReg2 database. It is expected that users would like to search the database for the development of new products using existing engineered nanomaterials (nano-objects) and for the development of new nano-objects. For the former the assessment of hazard and exposure of existing materials in a value chain in relation to functionality will be an important part of the database, while for the development of new materials the focus may be more on grouping and read-across.

Data Sources

The sources of data to feed the NanoReg2 database will be:

1. Published data.
2. Data from the **NR** database now with TNO (experimental data and literature data) and not yet accessible.
3. Data from other projects, that agree to cooperate with NanoReg2 (maybe published already or not), such as:
 - EU MARINA
 - EU NanoSolutions
 - EU NanoMILE
 - EU NanoTest
 - EU NanoValid
 - EU ENPRA
 - EU Guidenano
 - EU Calibrate
 - EU SUN
4. Data generated by this project, NanoReg2.

Confidentiality and data sources

Some of the WP2 data will be obtained from industrial partners and confidentiality issues may apply. Which data will be publicly available and what part is confidential? For SbD (WP3) we need an open data and information exchange, therefore, our aim is to create a publicly available database, i.e. also for those outside the project. The data concerning on the chemical-physical nanoparticles

characterization and toxicity are not confidential. However, all the information related to nanomaterials synthesis, procedures or any other process involved is strictly confidential unless specified otherwise.

There may be a requirement to be able to label data which needs to be kept confidential within the NanoReg2 project. Some of the companies providing data as part of the industrial case studies will be happy for this to be used for grouping and read across as part of the project, but would want this data removed from any public version of the database. Prior to companies being asked to include data in the database, it will also be necessary for them to be made aware of the use of the data outside and beyond the life of the project to allow them to assess any potential risk to confidential or IP sensitive information that they may include

Criteria for data import / entry tools

Data import must be easily and automatically possible via standardized excel templates (which yet need to be agreed/ defined) following eNanoMapper principles.

In general, data outputs from WPs 1 to4 are generated within the project and therefore specific input data formats should be produced and filled in a standardized manner.

More end points may be introduced as the project evolves to cover LCA and socio/economic assessment. This information should allow doing flexible RA depending on the WP2 pillar we are looking at (product, use/handling and production).

It should also allow choosing between the different developmental stages within the innovation chain. Perhaps different modules may be created for the different phases at the innovation chain. RA analysis will require different data at different stages (=stage gates from idea to market). Therefore the database must be complete enough, and accessible enough to perform these different analyses.

Manual data entry may be needed when the different experiments within the NanoReg2 project have different formats. When there are large amounts of data in the same format it would be efficient when they can be entered automatically (from e.g. Excel).

Data Format

The Data Format should be based on simple numerical characters, keeping wording to a minimum. Units should be previously agreed so all partners produced data in the same fashion.

The database should be able to support the most common formats, i.e. IUCLID, ISA-TAB Nano. IUCLID already has well described entry points.

Of course the database should include all relevant parameters that we already have identified and which we consider relevant for grouping. Existing parameters considered in the FP7 NANoREG project, and from e.g. ECHA, JRC, RIVM (DOI10.2823/982046) must be included such as phys-chem characterization data (pristine materials and materials in life cycle), toxicity, ecotoxicity and physical hazard testing data¹.

New parameters may come up during the project, and so it must be possible to easily add them, so flexibility is needed.

Ontology

There should be a use of Standard terminology, which has to be agreed upon by the Solution Team, and approved by the NEB.

As the main goal within WP1 is to develop grouping it is prerequisite that there is ontology behind this database which is connected to search functions!

¹ For more details, please refer to presentation of NanoReg2 grouping (T6, Bilbao to be found in CIRCA BC), where those parameters are listed.

It may be necessary as the project continues to implement new criteria or parameters (e.g. new PhysChem descriptors or new toxicity endpoints), so this must also be possible!

Content of the Database – general points

A main concern with current databases are that they appear to focus almost exclusively on phys-chem and hazard of pristine nanomaterials, but tend to include little if any exposure data/information. WP4 would like a NanoReg2 database to include the following data items:

- Exposure scenario and life cycle information (this could be done using the standard REACH use and proc categories)
- Process and operating conditions during the exposure scenario (according to the REACH exposure scenario templates)
- Exposure measurement data and associated exposure determinants; according the NECID database for occupational exposure

the type of data that would ideally be required includes:

- Data on the life cycle stage, exposure scenario and any exposure data (human and environmental) relevant for the case study
- Data on physical-chemical characterization of
 - o ENM as pristine material
 - o ENM during the exposure pathways (emission, dispersion, immision)
 - o Any matrix that the ENM is contained in
- Hazard information of
 - o ENM as pristine material
 - o ENM during the exposure pathways (emission, dispersion, immision)
 - o Any matrix that the ENM is contained in

In addition to the above, we will also aim to collect information / data to determine at what stage of the innovation and stage gate process the case study is operating. However, we will do not anticipate that this information will be included in the NanoReg2 database.

The following aspects may also be included in the database, but the solution team should specify the format in discussion with all partners and the database working group.

- Disposal and recycling data
- Future materials with other properties

Task 3.2 is collecting the safety information to be considered per stage, including the parameters which need to be addressed. This analysis will be performed during this project, and all parameters needed will become clear at a later time. Therefore, WP3 needs a flexible system, i.e. additional parameters can be included in the data model/database at all time.

Data linking

The database should enable linking to other databases with relevant data sets, e.g. omics-databases such as ArrayExpress and GEO, but later potentially also HTS databases, which are bound to appear. There should also be a link to data on micrometric forms of the substance. For example, a substance, which is toxic at the microscale, could show at least at the same toxicity level at the nano scale.

Search tools

It is absolutely necessary to have different types of search options linked to the NanoReg2 database, including:

- name
- CAS number
- different phys-chem parameters
- different toxicity endpoints
- free text search
- functionality
- application
- Biological endpoints for both tox and ectox
- Stage of Innovation process
- risk potential, i.e. solubility, stability, accumulation, genotoxicity, inflammation, ecotoxicity

Search tools should include WP2 pillar, innovation state and all parameters previously defined under types of data above.

Data export

We need to work with the data (e.g. perform different statistical analysis etc.), thus data export is fundamental, and the most commonly used format will be excel. This applies to all four WPs.

Parameter	WP1	WP2	WP3	comments
Physicochemical				
Chemical composition			X	
particle size		X	X	
shape		X	X	
Specific surface area		X	X	
surface charge			X	
surface functional groups			X	
Crystalline structure		X	X	
Reactivity		X		
Surface composition / shell		X	X	
Purity		X		
doping with specific element(s)			X	
Relative Density		X		
Dissolution / solubility		X	X	
Biodurability		X		
Bioaccumulation and persistence		X		
Zeta potential		X		
Identity related properties				
Transparency			X	
light adsorption			X	
super-paramagnetism			X	
luminescence			X	
sheet resistance			X	
mechanical properties			X	

Product				
NM as powder/dispersion/paste		X		
Product in Matrix		X		
Production quantity/y		X		
Major application sector		X		
Any safe handling SOPs		X		
Expected level of NM/product		X		
Raw material consumption/ton product		X		
Chemical waste/ton product		X		
Specific applications of NMs				
antimicrobial coating			X	
corrosion resistant coating			X	
magnetic data storage			X	
bioimaging			X	
photocatalytic air cleaning			X	
drug delivery			X	
tissue regeneration			X	
implant coating			X	
Tox data				
Genotoxicity/carcinogenicity		X	X	
Inhalation toxicity		X	X	
Acute dermal toxicity		X	X	
Skin irritation		X	X	
Eye irritation		X	X	
Sensitization		X	X	
Toxicity fish (ecotox)		X	X	
Toxicity bacteria (ecotox)		X	X	
Toxicity daphnia (ecotox)		X	X	
Ecotoxicity				
Ecotoxicological data		X		
Aquatic ecotoxicity (also marine species)		X		
Fishes ecotoxicity		X		
Cyanobacteria and microalgae Ecotoxicity		X		
invertebrates (i.e daphnids) ecotoxicity		X		
Benthic ecotoxicity		X		
Macrophytes ecotoxicity		X		
Invertebrates ecotoxicity		X		
Terrestrial ecotoxicity		X		
Higher plants ecotoxicity		X		
Invertebrates ecotoxicity		X		
Physical Hazard				
Flammability		X		
Explosibility		X		
Dustiness		X		
Chemical reactivity		X		

Hazard and Exposure related				
solubility in Water			X	
stability of coating			X	
accumulation potential in tissue			X	
uptake pathways			X	
Kinetic parameters			X	
crossing bio-barriers			X	
entering cells			X	
industrial environment exposure		X		
Environment		X		
occupational		X		
consumer		X		
release		X		
primary target of release		X		

Annex 2. Linking of tools input parameters with NanoReg2 and NECID database

Stoffenmanager Nano

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology term	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database
Does the product contain fibers / fiber like particles?	Aspect Ratio NPO_1365	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements
If yes, length versus diameter of the fiber / aspect ratio		P-CHEM/Aspect ratio	Use of ENM
If no, inhalation hazard		P-CHEM/Aspect ratio	N.A.
Do you know the exact concentration of the nano component in the product? (Yes/no)	Concentration PATO_0000033	N.A.	Concentration
Concentration			
Product name	Name C42614 Trivial name CHEMINF_000109	N.A.	Product name
Supplier	Supplier C43530		
Name nano component	Nanomaterial NPO_199	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements
Volume of the working room	N.A.	N.A.	Room volume
Ventilation of the working room	N.A.	N.A.	General ventilation
Is the working room being cleaned daily?	N.A.	N.A.	General housekeeping
Are inspections and maintenance of machines/ancillary equipment being done at least monthly to ensure good condition and proper functioning and performance?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Duration task	Duration EFO_0000433	N.A.	Activity duration
Frequency task	Frequency PATO_0000044	N.A.	per hour
		N.A.	Total activity duration in shift
		N.A.	Number of shift per day
Start date of period worked with the product	Datum value NPO_1779	N.A.	Date campaign began
End date of period worked with the product		N.A.	Date campaign ended
Last update date of additional registration		N.A.	N.A.
Production or usage volume in kg a year	N.A.	N.A.	Used amount
Characterize your task	N.A.	N.A.	Detailed process description
Number of exposed employees	N.A.	N.A.	Total number of workers exposed
Is personal protective equipment applied?	N.A.	N.A.	PPE
Local control measures	N.A.	N.A.	Local control
Is the task being carried out in the breathing zone of an employee (distance head-product <1 meter)?	N.A.	N.A.	Distance source to worker
If yes, Is there more than one employee carrying out the same task simultaneously?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Is the employee situated in a cabin?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

LICARA NanoScan

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology term	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term in NECID database	NanON Ontology
0. Nanoproduct and legislation				
Type of nanomaterial and application				
Which nanomaterial will be used?	Nanomaterial NPO_199 Core component NPO 1888	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
Specify 'Others' (if selected)				
Please specify additional nano subtype or indications / properties:	Crystal structure CHEMINF 000102	P-CHEM / Crystallite and Grain phase	Product form	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology term	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term in NECID database	NanON Ontology
In which type of application is the nanomaterial be used?	Application CHEBI_33232	N.A.	Activity kind	
Is this a completely new product with a new functionality (which cannot easily be compared with a conventional product)?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
If not, what conventional product is being replaced by the new nanoproduct? (this can also be 'doing nothing')	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
The product under evaluation is:	N.A.	N.A.	Used as	
What is the main function that the nanomaterial provides in your application?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
What is the appropriate unit to compare the nanoproduct with the conventional product? (It is only correct to compare the same functionality)	Unit of measurement NPO 1153	N.A.	N.A.	
In case you have selected 'Other' please specify:				
Nano-relevance				
Approach 1 (precautionary approach): Ranges of sizes of primary particles contained in the materials (free, bound or as aggregates or agglomerates)?	Nanoparticle NPO_707	Protocols/SEM	Particle size	
	Agglomerate ENM_9000001	Protocols/TEM		
	Aggregate ENM_9000002	P-CHEM / Granulometry / Particle size distribution		
Approach 2 (EU-proposed definition 2011/696/EU): Material containing primary particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or as an agglomerate and where, for 50% or more of the primary particles in the number size distribution, one or more external dimensions is in the size range 1 nm - 100 nmor (if the number size distribution is unknown). Material where the specific surface area by volume is greater than 60m2/cm3 or Material consists of fullerenes, graphene flakes or single wall nanotubes.	VSSA ENM_0000091	P-CHEM / Granulometry / Particle size distribution	Volume specific surface area	
	Agglomerate ENM_9000001			
	Aggregate ENM_9000002	P-CHEM / Specific surface area		
Legislation				
Are you aware of existing legislation (e.g. EU Nr. 1907/2006 (REACH), The EU Biocides Regulation 528/2012 (EU BPR), Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 on cosmetic products ...)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Is your nanomaterial approved or notified according to relevant EU-legislation (e.g. EU Nr. 1907/2006 (REACH), The EU Biocides Regulation 528/2012 (EU BPR), Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 on cosmetic products ...)	N.A.	N.A.	OECD	
Do you use the nanomaterial below its specific concentration limits recommended in the legal framework (e.g. http://ec.europa.eu/environment/chemicals/biocides/active-substances/approved-substances_en.htm)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
1. Environmental benefits				
<i>Manufacturing phase of the nanoproduct versus conventional product</i>				
Energy consumption of the manufacturing process	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Materials consumption in this manufacturing process?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amounts of hazardous substances used in the manufacture?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Efforts needed to produce the product using the nanomaterial?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amount of solid waste from the manufacturing process?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amount of waste water from the manufacturing process?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Emissions to the air or (waste) water from the manufacturing process itself?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Use phase (only for final products and articles)</i>				
Product life time (use phase)?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Need for maintenance?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amounts of hazardous substances used in maintenance?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amount of solid waste from using the product?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amount of waste water resulting from use of the product?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Emissions of hazardous substances to air, water and/or solid?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Efficiency of use?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>End-of-life (only for final products and articles)</i>				
Volume of waste (due to e.g. longer lifetime, less weight, less material used)?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amounts of other hazardous substances released from the waste water treatment?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amounts of other hazardous substances released during incineration?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Established recycling systems (glass, PET, paper, carton, batteries, biowaste, electronic devices, etc.) exposed to the nanomaterial in the product?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Can the waste water treatment facility eliminate the nanoproduct's emissions?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Can the waste incineration facility eliminate the nanoproduct's emissions?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
2. Economic benefits				
<i>Market potential</i>				
Does the nanoproduct have increased marketability due to an improved functionality or a new functionality (for example: UV-protection, enhanced photolytical self-cleaning/ self-cleaning capacity/property, conductible, antimicrobial function), or a clear image advantage compared to the	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology term	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term in NECID database	NanON Ontology
conventional product (e.g.: more resistant to environmental effects, prolonged lifetime/persistence, reduced weight or increased strength)?				
What is the foreseen market potential of the nanoproduct or -application in Europe?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Profitability				
What is the (expected) purchase price per unit of the nanobased product or material compared to the conventional one?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
What are the operational costs (i.e. maintenance, energy use etc) during the use phase of the nanobased product or application compared to the conventional one? (Think of advantages due to nanoproperties in the manufacturing process)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Development stage				
What is the time-to-market to manufacture the nanoproduct on a commercial scale?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
3. Societal benefits				
Technological breakthrough				
Could the use or application of the nanoproduct be considered a technological breakthrough (in general, but particularly in energy systems and Information and Communication Technologies, ICT) compared to the conventional alternative?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Highly qualified labour force				
Does the production of the application lead to a substantial improvement in the development of a highly qualified labour force compared to the conventional alternative?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Improving global health or food situation				
Compared to the conventional alternative... OR Does the use or application of the nano-based product lead to improvements in people's health, particularly the direct user, e.g. by improvements in water purity, sanitation or medicines and pharmaceuticals?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
4. Public health & environmental risks				
System knowledge				
Is the origin of the (nanoscale) starting materials known?	Mineral material ENVO_01000256	N.A.	N.A.	
	Chemical substance CHEBI_59999			
Are the next users of the nanomaterials under consideration known?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
How accurately is the material system known or can disturbing factors (e.g. impurities) be estimated?	composition chemical ENM_0000082	Method/ICP-MS	Ingredients	
		P-CHEM/ICP-MS-Al or Co or Fe or Na		
		Protocols/EDX or ICP-OES or SAXS or WAXS		
		Protocols/Chemical composition		
		P-CHEM/ IMPURITIES- Al or C or Ce or Cl or F or N or Na or O or P or S or Si or Ti	Purity	
		P-CHEM/ OTHER ELEMENT/IMPURITIES - Al or Co or Cr or Fe or Free Ag or Mn or Ni or Pb or V or Zn		
Potential effect				
Do the nanomaterials cause redox activity, catalytic activity or have a potential for oxygen radical formation or to induce inflammation reactions? (The drop-down menu gives clues which forms of nanoproducts have a low, medium or high potential effect.)	Reactive oxygen species generator CHEBI_70982	TOX / Oxidative stress	N.A.	
	Oxidative stress ENM_0000037	P-CHEM / Physchem other / Redox Potential		
	Inflammatory AE OAE_0000557			
What is the stability (half-life) of the nanoparticles present in the nanomaterial under ambient environmental conditions?	Half-life UO_0000152		N.A.	
Potential input into the environment				
What is the annual quantity of nanoparticles from the manufacturing phase that reaches the environment via wastewater, exhaust gases or solid waste?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
What is the physical surrounding or carrier material of the nanoparticles in the product during the use phase?	Physical state NPO 888	Protocols/SEM Protocols/TEM	Physical state	
What is the annual quantity of nanoparticles in products that reaches from production or use phase the environment via utility products, waste water, exhaust gases or solid waste?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
What is the annual quantity of disposed nanomaterial (from the production or use phase)?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
5. Occupational health risks				
Hazard & exposure during manufacture of the nanomaterial	Via Stoffenmanager nano			
Hazard & exposure during processing the nanomaterial				
Hazard & exposure during application of the nanoproduct				
6. Consumer health risks				

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology term	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term in NECID database	NanON Ontology
<i>Hazard & exposure by consumers during use phase</i>				
At what location is the nanoelement situated in the article or the product? The product...	N.A.	Protocols/SEM or TEM	N.A.	
What is the size of the consumer population using the nanoproduct and hence which may be exposed?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

FNN-BNN

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
<i>Material variables</i>				
Hardness composite (Mohs scale)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Nano object size	Particle diameter NPO_1539	P-CHEM / Particle Size distribution	Particle size	
	Primary particle NPO_1896			
Isotropy composite	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Toughness composite	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Brittleness composite	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Particles nano in composite (%)	Mass percentage UO_0000163	P-CHEM / Particle Size distribution / Physchem (other) / ICP-MS-AL or ICP-MS-CO or ICP-MS-FE	N.A.	
Affinity nanomaterial in matrix	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Dispersion state	N.A.	P-CHEM / Aggregation state	N.A.	
<i>Process variables</i>				
Primary or secondary shredder	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Number of shafts	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Width of knives	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Number of teeth	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Sieve used	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Input size	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Output size	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

NanoRiskCat

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Scenario(s) and nanomaterial identification				
<i>Nanomaterial description</i>				
Material Sourcing (e.g. producer, supplier)	Supplier C43530	Study providers/vial ID	Eg. Manufacturer, Catalogue number, batch number	
Manufacturing (e.g. processing, product fabrication, filling/packaging)	Material synthesis technique NPO_1921	N.A.	Detailed process description	
Appearance (e.g. black powder, yellow paste, transparent liquid)	Physical state NPO_888	N.A.	Physical state	
Chemical composition- Molecular formula	IUPAC chemical formula CHEMINF_000037	N.A.	N.A.	
Physical form/shape	Shape NPO_274	Protocols/SEM or TEM	N.A.	
	Physical state NPO_888	P-CHEM/Aspect ratio		
Purity	Purity percentage UO_0000193	P-CHEM/ IMPURITIES- Al or C or Ce or Cl or F or N or Na or O or P or S or Si or Ti	Purity	
		P-CHEM/ OTHER ELEMENT/IMPURITIES - Al or Co or Cr or Fe or Free Ag or Mn or Ni or Pb or V or Zn		
		P-CHEM/ICP-MS-Al or Co or Fe or Na		
Size distribution	particle size distribution NPO_1699	P-CHEM/Particle size distribution	N.A.	
Solubility in water	Solubility in water NPO_500	P-CHEM/Water solubility	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
State of aggregation or agglomeration	N.A.	Protocols/SEM or TEM	N.A.	
CAS number (if applicable)	CAS registry number CHEMINF_000446	Nanomaterial type/ IUC Substance/CAS	CAS	
Material life-cycle stage				
Distribution	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Use/maintenance/reuse	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Disposal/Recycling	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Location of the nanoscale structure in the system	Nanostructured material NPO_1910	Protocols/SEM or TEM Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy	N.A.	
Criteria for evaluating the exposure profile				
Applicable Process categories (PROCs)	N.A.	N.A.	Description activity	
Chemical Product Categories (PCs)	Application CHEBI_33232	N.A.	Product kind	
Functional categories (FCs)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Article categories (ACs)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Environmental Release Categories (ERCs)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Criteria for evaluating the potential human health hazards				
Does the nanomaterial fulfil the HARN paradigm?	Aspect ratio NPO_1365	P-CHEM/Aspect Ratio Nanomaterial type	N.A.	
Is the bulk form of the nanomaterial known to cause or may cause serious damaging effects?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Is the bulk form of the nanomaterial classified for other less severe adverse effects according to the CLP such as skin corrosion/irritation category 2 and specific target organ toxicity-single exposure category 3?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Is the specific nanomaterial known to be acute toxic?	Acute dermal toxicity ENM_0000026 Acute oral toxicity ENM_0000020 Acute inhalation toxicity ENM_0000023	TOX	N.A.	
Are there indications that the nanomaterial causes genotoxic, mutagenic, carcinogenic, respiratory, cardiovascular neurotoxic or reproductive effects in humans and/or laboratory animals or has organspecific accumulation been documented?	Carcinogenicity ENM_0000029 Cytotoxicity NPO_1340 Dermal toxicity ENM_0000025 Developmental toxicity ENM_0000050 Genetic toxicity ENM_0000028 Immunotoxicity NPO_1339 Inhalation toxicity ENM_0000022 Oral toxicity ENM_0000019 Reproductive toxicity ENM_0000030	TOX	N.A.	
Criteria for evaluating the environmental hazard profile				
Is the nanomaterial in question reported to be hazardous to environmental species?	Environmental toxicity ENM_0000001	ECOTOX	N.A.	
Is the nanomaterial in question persistent?	N.A.			
Is the nanomaterial in question bioaccumulative?	N.A.			
Could use of the nanomaterial in question lead to potentially irreversible harm to the environment (e.g. ecosystem effects)?	N.A.			
Is the nanomaterial in question readily dispersed?	N.A.			
Is the nanomaterial in question novel?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Material Identifiers				
Material name	Core component NPO_1888	Nanomaterial type	Product name	
Manufacturer	N.A.	Study providers/vial ID	Eg. Manufacturer, Catalogue number, batch number	
CAS number	CAS registry number CHEMINF_000446	Nanomaterial type/ IUC Substance/CAS	CAS	
EINECS	EINECS No. CHEMINF_000447	Nanomaterial type/ IUC Substance/EC	N.A.	
Material Information				
Is the material named with a nano-specific word or term e.g. nano, dot, cluster, fulleoid, fullerol, quantum, ...?	Nanomaterial NPO_199	N.A.	Product name	
Is the material coated or surface modified or functionalized?	surface-functionalized nanoparticle NPO_1881	Protocols/SEM or TEM	Coating	
		Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy		
Is the shape of the primary particles known?	Shape	Protocols/SEM or TEM, Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy, P- CHEM/Aspect ratio	N.A.	
Morphology				
Dimensions of the primary particles	size TEM ENM_8000295	Protocols/SEM or TEM	Particle size	
	size and PSD sp-ICP- MS ENM_8000296	P-CHEM/BET		
	size_XRD ENM_8000299	Protocols/XRD		
What is the surface area of the powder material?	VSSA ENM_0000091	P-CHEM/BET	N.A.	
What is the relative density (specific gravity) of the material?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
What is the solubility of the material in water?	Solubility in water NPO_500	P-CHEM/Water solubility	N.A.	
What is the respirable dustiness index?	N.A.	P-CHEM/Dustiness/ Respirable dustiness index	N.A.	
Safety data				
Nanospecific OEL	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Exposure limit for respirable dust	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Select type of toxicological information (Risk sentences / GHS-CLP hazard statements)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
General toxicity- Applicable risk sentence(s)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
GHS/CLP Hazard statement codes	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Carcinogenic effect	Carcinogenicity ENM_0000029		N.A.	
Reprotoxicity	Reproductive toxicity ENM_0000030		N.A.	
Neurotoxicity	N.A.		N.A.	
Allergy and Sensitization	Skin irritation ENM_0000032		N.A.	
	Skin sensitization ENM_0000034			
Process				
Name the work situation or process to be modelled	macroscopic synthesis part NPO_1945	N.A.	N.A.	
Energy level	N.A.	N.A.	Activity kind	
Enter the total amount of nanomaterial used per cycle at the workstation	N.A.	N.A.	Amount used	
How long does it take to perform one cycle at the work station?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
How many minutes pass between each work cycle?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
How many times is the work cycle repeated daily?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Enter the mass handled per scoop, bag, big-bag etc. in the work cycle	N.A.	N.A.	Material used rate	
Enter the time required to pour one scoop, bag, big-bag etc. in the work cycle	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Work area				
Length of workroom	Length PATO_0000122	N.A.	Room length	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Width of workroom	Width PATO_0000921	N.A.	Room width	
Height of workroom	Height PATO_0000119	N.A.	Room height	
No. of air-exchange in the work room per hour	N.A.	N.A.	Air change	
Activity level in the work room	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Precautionary Matrix

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
General Information				
Precautionary matrix completed by / responsible contact person	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Brief description of the considered nanospecific field (type of nanomaterials, which surrounding, in which application)	Nanoparticle NPO_707	N.A.	N.A.	
	Core component NPO_1888			
	Application CHEBI_33232			
Brief description of the considered (process) step (production, packaging, transport, further stages of processing, disposal, use...), brief description	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Scenario: Calculation of the precautionary need	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Are coated / functionalised nanomaterials involved?	surface modified nanoparticle NPO_1885	Protocols/SEM or TEM	Coating	
	surface-functionalized nanoparticle NPO_1881	Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy		
Relevance				
"Material containing primary particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or as an agglomerate and where, for 50% or more of the primary particles in the number size distribution, one or more external dimensions is in the size range 1 nm - 100 nm or Material where the specific surface area by volume is greater than 60m ² /cm ³ or Material consists of fullerenes, graphene flakes or single wall nanotubes."	Nanoparticle NPO_707	P-CHEM / Granulometry / Particle size distribution	Particle size	
	Agglomerate ENM_9000001			
	Aggregate ENM_9000002	P-CHEM / Specific surface area	Volume specific surface area	
Do you want to include primary particles from 1 to 500 nm in your evaluation?	Primary particle NPO_1896	N.A.	N.A.	
Order of size of the primary particles in the materials (free, bound, aggregated or agglomerated)	primary particle NPO_1896	Protocols/SEM or TEM	Particle size	
	particle size distribution NPO_1699	P-CHEM/BET		
	particle diameter NPO_1539	Protocols/XRD	BET	
Do the primary particles form agglomerates >500 nm?	particle size distribution NPO_1699	P-CHEM/Particle size distribution	N.A.	
	Agglomerate ENM_9000001	Protocols/Nanoparticles Tracking Analysis or SEM or XRD or TEM or SAXS or WAXS or DLS or Aerosol Characterization or sp-ICP-MS		
In the body does deagglomeration of agglomerates (or aggregates) to primary particles or agglomerates <500 nm occur?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
If agglomerates between 500 nm and 10µm are present, can employees or consumers take them in through their lungs?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Under the respective environmental conditions does deagglomeration of agglomerates (or aggregates) to primary particles or agglomerates <500 nm occur?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Uncertainties				
Is the origin of the (nanoscale) starting materials known?	mineral material ENVO_01000256	N.A.	N.A.	
	chemical substance CHEBI_59999			
Is sufficient information available to complete the precautionary matrix for nanoscale starting materials?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Are the subsequent users of the considered nanomaterials known?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
How accurately is the material system known, or can disturbing factors (e.g. impurities) be estimated?	composition chemical ENM_0000082	Method/ICP-MS P-CHEM/ICP-MS-Al or Co or Fe or Na Protocols/EDX or ICP-OES or SAXS or WAXS Protocols/Chemical composition P-CHEM/ IMPURITIES-Al or C or Ce or Cl or F or N or Na or O or P or S or Si or Ti P-CHEM/ OTHER ELEMENT/IMPURITIES-Al or Co or Cr or Fe or Free Ag or Mn or Ni or Pb or V or Zn	N.A.	
Potential Effect				
<i>Reactivity</i>				
Redox activity of the nanomaterial	N.A.	P-CHEM/Physchem (other)/Redox Potential	N.A.	
Catalytic activity of the nanomaterial	N.A.		N.A.	
Oxygen radical formation potential of the nanomaterial	Oxidative stress ENM_0000037 reactive oxygen species generator CHEBI_70982	TOX/Oxidative stress Method/Oxidative stress or ROS	N.A.	
Induction potential for inflammatory reactions of the nanomaterial	Inflammation AE OAE 0000557		N.A.	
<i>Stability</i>				
Stability (half-life) of the primary particles present in the nanomaterial in the body	Half-life UO_0000152	N.A.	N.A.	
Stability (half-life) of the primary particles present in the nanomaterial under environmental conditions				
Exposition				
Carrier material- Physical surrounding of the nanomaterial	Physical state NPO 888	Protocols/SEM or TEM Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy	N.A.	
<i>Maximum possible exposure of humans</i>				
Amount of nanomaterials which a worker handles per day	N.A.	N.A.	Amount used	
Amount of nanomaterials with which a worker comes into contact in the "worst case"	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Frequency with which a worker handles the nanomaterial	Frequency PATO_0000044	N.A.	Number of shifts per day	
Amount of nanomaterials which a consumer handles daily through the utility product	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Frequency with which a consumer uses the utility product	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Maximum possible input into the environment</i>				
Amount of nanomaterials that during the production phase reaches the environment from wastewater, exhaust gases, solid waste per year	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amount of nanomaterials in utility products per year	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Amount of disposed nanomaterials per year	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Guide Nano

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Case				
Name of the case	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
General description and Goal	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Visual start date	Datum value NPO_1779	N.A.	N.A.	
Authors	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Activities				
Activity name	material synthesis technique NPO_1921	N.A.	Source domain	
Setting/Scale	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Life cycle phase	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Location	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>General info</i>				
Description	N.A.	N.A.	Description activity	
Handling type	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Applied energy level	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Concurrent Locations	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Input, Output and Release</i>				
<i>Activity input</i>				
Input description	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Material	Core Component NPO_1888	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
Relative amount	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Total amount	Mass PATO_0000125 Volume PATO_0000918	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	Mass unit UO_0000002 Volume unit UO_0000095	N.A.	N.A.	
Is the operational time of this activity relative to the input amount?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Rate metric	Rate unit UO_0000280	N.A.	Material used rate	
Rate	Rate PATO_0000161	N.A.	Material used rate	
<i>Activity output(s)</i>				
Output description	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Material	Core Component NPO_1888	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
<i>Activity release(s)</i>				
Release description	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Released material	Core Component NPO_1888	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
Relative to	Core Component NPO_1888	N.A.	N.A.	
Relative release or relative amount	Mass PATO_0000125 Volume PATO_0000918 Particle concentration NPO_1830	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	Percent UO_0000187	N.A.	N.A.	
Data source	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
RMM's	N.A.	N.A.	RMM	
Rate/location	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Duration</i>				
Activity repetition	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Number of times this activity is applied for the same batch	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Operational time	N.A.	N.A.	Activity duration	
Operational time unit	time unit UO_0000003	N.A.		
Time span	N.A.	N.A.	Total activity duration in shift	
Time span unit	time unit UO_0000003	N.A.		
<i>(Nano)material flow</i>				
Input from preceding activity	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Output to succeeding activity	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Transport time	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	Time unit UO_0000003	N.A.	N.A.	
Release into compartment zone	Environmental material ENVO_00010483	N.A.	N.A.	
Release directly in contact with	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Local controls</i>				
Local controls	N.A.	N.A.	Local control	
Redirected towards	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Efficacy value	N.A.	N.A.	Efficiency of room ventilation RMM class	
<i>(Nano)materials</i>				
<i>Product</i>				
<i>Identification</i>				
Product name	Trivial name CHEMINF_000109	Nanomaterial type	Product name	
Description	Batch number C104504	N.A.	Product ID Product form	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
	Information content entity IAO_0000030		Ingredients	
			Purity of material	
Origin	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Source/origin	N.A.	Study providers/vial ID	Eg. Manufacturer, Catalogue number, batch number	
<i>Components</i>				
Phase	Physical state NPO_888	N.A.	Physical state	
role of the component	Molecular component in nanoparticle NPO_1495	Protocols/SEM or TEM Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy	N.A.	
amount/item	Mass PATO_0000125	N.A.	N.A.	
unit	Mass unit UO_0000002	N.A.	Mass unit	
mass perc.	Mass percentage UO_0000163	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Mass conversion</i>				
Length	Length PATO_0000122 Length unit UO_0000001	N.A.	N.A.	
Surface area	Surface area CHEMINF_000247	N.A.	N.A.	
Volume	Volume PATO_0000918 Volume unit UO_0000095	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Material(s) or Substance(s)</i>				
<i>Physicochemical characteristics</i>				
<i>Single Chemical</i>				
<i>Identification</i>				
Chemically identified by	Identifying descriptor CHEMINF_000061	Nanomaterial type/Material or Composition	Molecular mass CAS	
CAS number	CAS registry number CHEMINF_000446	Nanomaterial type/IUC Substance/CAS	CAS	
EC number	EINECS No CHEMINF_000447	Nanomaterial type/IUC Substance/EC	N.A.	
Chemical name	IUPAC name CHEMINF_000107	Nanomaterial type/IUC Substance/Chemical name	N.A.	
Molecular formula	Molecular formula CHEMINF_000042	Nanomaterial type/IUC Substance/Molecular formula	N.A.	
Molecule group	N.A.	Nanomaterial type	N.A.	
Density	Density ENM_0000084	P-CHEM/Physchem (other)/ Density	Density	
Chemistry	N.A.	Method/ICP-MS Protocols/EDX or ICP-OES or SAXS or WAXS Protocols/Chemical composition P-CHEM/Zeta potential	N.A.	
<i>Physical properties</i>				
Melting point in °C	Melting point descriptor CHEMINF_000256	N.A.	N.A.	
Boiling point in °C	Boiling point ENM_9000100	N.A.	N.A.	
Size category	Size value NPO_1807 Particle size NPO_1694	Protocols/SEM or TEM Method/Optical microscopy or STEM	Particle size	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
		P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution		
		P-CHEM/ Crystallite_grain phase/Crystallite size or 1st average or 2nd average		
Rigidity	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Internal structure	Crystalline state NPO_1512	P-CHEM/ Crystalline phase or Crystalline and grain phase	N.A.	
		Protocols/SAXS or WAXS		
Crystalline form	Crystalline state NPO_1512	P-CHEM/ Crystalline phase or Crystalline and grain phase	N.A.	
		Protocols/SAXS or WAXS		
Space group	Space group ENM_9000037	P-CHEM/ Crystalline phase or Crystalline and grain phase	N.A.	
Crystallite size	N.A.	Protocols/SAXS or WAXS	N.A.	
Name of the mineral	Mineral material ENVO_01000256	Protocols/SAXS or WAXS	N.A.	
% of purity of crystalline phase	N.A.	Protocols/SAXS or WAXS	N.A.	
Reactivity info				
Solubility	Solubility PATO_0001536	P-CHEM/Water solubility	N.A.	
Indicate the reactivity	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Classification and labelling				
Hazard statements	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Combination/Mixture				
Identification				
Substance name	N.A.	N.A.	Product name	
Source/origin	N.A.	Study providers/vial ID	Eg. Manufacturer, Catalogue number, batch number	
Physical properties				
How does the liquid present itself?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
What is the viscosity of the fluid?	N.A.	N.A.	viscosity	
Surface properties				
Contact order	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Chemical info				
Are all constituents, impurities and contaminants added and identified and Purity in %?	Composition C53414	Method/EDX	Ingredients	
		P-CHEM/ICP-MS-Al or Co or Fe or Na		
		P-CHEM/ IMPURITIES-Al or C or Ce or Cl or F or N or Na or O or P or S or Si or Ti	Purity	
		P-CHEM/ OTHER ELEMENT/ IMPURITIES- Al or Co or Cr or Fe or Free Ag or Mn or Ni or Pb or V or Zn		
		P-CHEM/ICP-MS-Al or Co or Fe or Na		
Function(s)				
Indicate the function(s)	Application CHEBI_33232	N.A.	N.A.	
Mass conversion				
Other metrics besides mass to express an amount of this material in	Volume PATO_0000918	N.A.	N.A.	
	Surface area NPO_1235			
	Length PATO_0000122			
Indicate which mass unit is convenient to express an amount of this material in	Mass unit UO_0000002	N.A.	Mass Unit	
The mass of this material per volume (mass density)	Volumetric density PATO_0001353	P-CHEM/Physchem (other)/Density	Density	
		P-CHEM/PC DENSITY SECTION/Density or Particle Density		
Units	Mass density unit UO_0000052	N.A.	Density unit	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
The mass of this material per surface area	Area density PATO_0001351	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	Area density unit UO_0000054	N.A.	N.A.	
The mass of this material per length	Linear density PATO_0001352	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	Linear density unit UO_0000183	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Nano-object</i>				
<i>Physical properties</i>				
Physical state of this material	Physical state NPO_888	N.A.	Physical state	
Dustiness [mg/kg]	Dustiness ENM_9000003	P-CHEM/Dustiness	Dustiness	
		Protocols/Dustiness		
<i>Shape and size</i>				
Morphology/shape	Shape NPO_274	P-CHEM/Aspect Ratio	N.A.	
		Protocols/SEM or TEM		
		Method/Optical microscopy or STEM or Confocal microscopy		
Size distribution available	Particle size distribution NPO_1699	P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution	N.A.	
If sphere, mean nanoscaled particle diameter (D1 ~ D2 ~ D3) in nm	Spherical shape NPO_286	Protocols/TEM/ MEAN FERET MINIMAL DIAMETER or MEAN ECD	N.A.	
	D1 ENM_9000101			
	D2 ENM_9000102			
	D3 ENM_9000103			
If cube, Mean nanoscaled particle size (D1, shortest dimension) in nm	Cubical shape NPO_861	Protocols/TEM/ MEAN FERET MINIMAL DIAMETER or MEAN ECD	N.A.	
If cube, mean nanoscaled particle size (D2, next sized dimension) in nm			N.A.	
If cube, mean nanoscaled particle size (D3, largest dimension) in nm			N.A.	
If wires, mean nanoscaled fibre diameter (D1 ~ D2) in nm	N.A.	Protocols/TEM/ MEAN FERET MINIMAL DIAMETER or MEAN ECD	N.A.	
If wires, mean fibre length (D3, largest dimension >> 100nm) in nm			N.A.	
If platelets, mean nanoscaled plate/disc/film thickness (D1, smallest dimension) in nm	Disc-shaped NPO_307	Protocols/TEM/ MEAN FERET MINIMAL DIAMETER or MEAN ECD	N.A.	
If platelets, mean width of the plate/film (D2, >> 100nm) in nm			N.A.	
If platelets, mean length of the plate/film (D3, >> 100nm) in nm			N.A.	
Method used and Primary size	size PTA ENM_8000293	P-CHEM/Particle size distribution or BET	N.A.	
	size SAXS ENM_8000294			
	size TEM ENM_8000295			
	size and PSD sp-ICP-MS ENM_8000296	Protocols/Nanoparticles Tracking Analysis or SEM or XRD or TEM or SAXS or WAXS or DLS or Aerosol Characterization or sp-ICP-MS		
	size_DLS ENM_8000297			
	size_WAXD ENM_8000298			
	size_XRD ENM_8000299			
Aerodynamic size	N.A.	Protocols/ Aerosol Characterization	N.A.	
Hydrodynamic size	Hydrodynamic size NPO_1914	P-CHEM/Particle size distribution/Hydrodynamic size	N.A.	
		Protocols/DLS		
Size distribution metric	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Size distribution type	Normal distribution OBCS_0000005	N.A.	N.A.	
	Log-normal distribution OBCS_0000008			
Mean size in nm	mean particle size NPO_1822	P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/Mean particle size	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Standard deviation	standard deviation NPO_1804	P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/standard dev	N.A.	
Geometric mean size in nm	N.A.	P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/Geometric mean size	N.A.	
Geometric standard deviation	N.A.	P-CHEM/ Particle size distribution/geometric standard dev	N.A.	
<i>Surface properties</i>				
Mass specific surface area in [m2/g]	Specific surface area CHEMINF_000515	N.A.	N.A.	
Surface charge	Surface charge NPO_1812	N.A.	N.A.	
Zeta potential	Zeta potential value NPO_1815	P-CHEM/Zeta potential	N.A.	
Surface potential medium	Medium NPO_1853	Medium	N.A.	
pH value of medium used	pH value NPO_1814	P-CHEM/Initial pH or Final pH	N.A.	
Hydrophobicity/Hydrophilicity			N.A.	
<i>Mass conversion</i>				
Other metrics besides mass to express an amount of this material in	Mole UO_0000013	N.A.	N.A.	
Molar mass in [g/mol]:	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
The number of particles per mass of this material	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Compartments				
<i>Indoor air</i>				
<i>General</i>				
Description	N.A.	N.A.	Description of the workplace	
Width of the room	Width PATO_0000921	N.A.	Room width	
Units	Length unit UO_0000001	N.A.	N.A.	
Length of the room	Length PATO_0000122	N.A.	Room length	
Units	Length unit UO_0000001	N.A.	N.A.	
Area of the room	Surface area NPO_1235	N.A.	Room width	
			Room length	
Units	Area unit UO_0000047	N.A.	N.A.	
Height of the room	Height PATO_0000119	N.A.	Room height	
Units	Length unit UO_0000001	N.A.	N.A.	
Volume of the room	Volume PATO_0000918	N.A.	Room width	
			Room length	
			Room height	
Units	Volume unit UO_0000095	N.A.	N.A.	
Deposition surface in [m2]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Zones</i>				
Zone description	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Number	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Medium	Environmental material ENVO_00010483	N.A.	N.A.	
Size	Size PATO_0000117	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	Area unit UO_0000047	N.A.	N.A.	
	Volume unit UO_0000095			
<i>Properties</i>				
Temperature	temperature value NPO_1806	N.A.	Temperature in °C	
Units	Temperature unit UO_0000126	N.A.		
Pressure	N.A.	N.A.	Air pressure in bars	
Units	Pressure unit UO_0000109	N.A.		
Mechanical ventilation	N.A.	N.A.	General ventilation	
Air exchanges per hour [/h]	N.A.	N.A.	Air changes	
Ventilation rate in [l/s]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
pH	pH value NPO_1814	P-CHEM/Initial pH or Final pH	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Ionic strength [mol/l]	N.A.	P-CHEM/ Solubility in organic solvents/Sample ionic concentration	N.A.	
Salinity [kg/m3]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Photo active depth [m]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Water exchanges per hour [/h]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Water flow rate [m3/s]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Flow type	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Flow velocity [m/s]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Porosity at the water interface [m3/m3]	Porosity PATO_0000973	N.A.	N.A.	
Rate of decrease in porosity with depth [/m]:	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Sand content in %	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Clay content in %	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Silt content in %	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Compaction class	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Packing density [ton/m3]	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Composition				
name/identifier	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
phase	physical state NPO_888	N.A.	N.A.	
role of constituent	Dissolved PATO_0001986	N.A.	N.A.	
	gaseous state NPO_1502			
Concentration	Concentration PATO_0000033	N.A.	N.A.	
Concentration metrics A/B	Concentration unit	N.A.	N.A.	
Concentration units A/B	UO_0000051	N.A.	N.A.	
Contact zones				
In contact with	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Orientation	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Separated	Barrier ENM_8000173	N.A.	N.A.	
Immission(s)				
<i>Exposed</i>				
Select or add a new exposed human population or eco species	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Exposure/Hazard Assessment				
<i>Human populations</i>				
Population name	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Group	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Workers</i>				
<i>General</i>				
Population name	N.A.	N.A.	Worker ID	
Description	N.A.	N.A.	Exposure pattern	
Body weight [kg]	Body weight EFO_0004338	N.A.	N.A.	
Total working years	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Workweeks a year	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Workdays a week	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Working hours a day	N.A.	N.A.	Shift duration	
			No. of shifts per day	
Available protective controls				
Name	N.A.	N.A.	PPE	
Efficacy inhalation	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Efficacy dermal	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Efficacy oral	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Exposure paths				
<i>Indirect through zone(s)</i>				
Exposure zone(s)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Route	Exposure Route of Administration C83121	Exposure Route	N.A.	
Exposure relevant material	N.A.	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
Concentration estimate(s)				
Source/Model	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Peak concentration	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Long term concentration	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	Concentration unit UO_0000051	N.A.	N.A.	
Use	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Population presence				
Total timespan to consider	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
During	Duration EFO_0000433	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	time unit UO_0000003	N.A.	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Frequency	Frequency PATO_0000044	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	Frequency unit UO_0000105	N.A.	N.A.	
Period of presence in zone	Duration EFO_0000433	N.A.	N.A.	
Units	time unit UO_0000003	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Direct contact</i>				
Description	N.A.	N.A.	Exposure pattern	
Direct route	N.A.	Exposure Route	N.A.	
Applied product/material	N.A.	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
Duration of contact	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Hazard assessment</i>				
Are there regulatory binding or provisional OELs/DNELs for the exposure relevant material?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Dose descriptor	N.A.	TOX/concentration	N.A.	
Critical dose	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Duration	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Source/Comment	Information resource ENM_8000073	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Consumers</i>				
Maximum number of years of consumer availability (consumption)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>By stander(s)</i>				
Duration between the first presence of the bystander (population) in this zone up until the last presence	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	time unit UO_0000003	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Species</i>				
<i>Exposure paths</i>				
Exposure zone	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Exposure Relevant material	Nanomaterial NPO_199 Core Component NPO 1888	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
Source/model	Information resource ENM_8000073	N.A.	N.A.	
Peak concentration	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Long term concentration	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Use	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Exposure scenarios</i>				
Description	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Contributing path(s)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
<i>Hazard Assessment</i>				
<i>Toxicity study</i>				
<i>Human health studies</i>				
<i>Eco studies</i>				
Is there toxicity studies with the exposure relevant material or similar material?	toxicity assay BAO_0002189	Nanomaterial type	N.A.	
Human health studies	Toxicological endpoint ENM_0000018	Studies/Tox/Protocol	N.A.	
Outcome	N.A.	Studies/Tox/(aggregated) Results	N.A.	
Effect levels	N.A.	Studies/Tox/(aggregated) Results	N.A.	
Measured endpoint	N.A.	Tox/Endpoint	N.A.	
Concentration type	Response endpoint BAO_0000181	N.A.	N.A.	
Effect concentration	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Unit	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Study duration	Duration EFO_0000433	TOX/exposure time	N.A.	
<i>Studied/administered material</i>				
Presence of a vehicle/carrier in the studied/administered (nano)material	N.A.		N.A.	
Indicate the administered substance	N.A.		N.A.	
Indicate the constituents of the administered substance	N.A.		N.A.	
<i>Test eco-medium</i>				
Is the administered substance dispersed into an eco-medium?	N.A.	Dispersion protocol/Medium	N.A.	
Indicate the eco-medium used in this study	N.A.	Dispersion protocol/Medium	N.A.	
<i>Species used</i>				
Species used	N.A.	E.Animal model	N.A.	
Number of animals used per dose group	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Administrative route of exposure	N.A.	Route of administration	N.A.	

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Method of inhalation exposure used	N.A.	E.exposure_method	N.A.	
Duration of exposure in [h/day]	N.A.	E.exposure_time	N.A.	
Observed effect				
<i>Effect level(s)</i>				
Measured endpoint	N.A.	Endpoint	N.A.	
Concentration type	N.A.		N.A.	
Effect concentration	N.A.		N.A.	
Unit	N.A.		N.A.	
Study duration	N.A.		N.A.	
<i>Quality</i>				
GLP (Good Laboratory Practice)?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Test substance identification	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Score	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	

Control banding Nanotool

Input data name	eNanoMapper Ontology term	Filtered entry for NanoReg2 database	Corresponding term for NECID database	NanON Ontology
Scenario description	N.A.	N.A.	Detailed process description	
Name or description of nanomaterial	Core component NPO 1888 Nanomaterial NPO_199	Nanomaterial type	ENM of interest for this set of measurements	
CAS#	CAS Registry number CHEMINF 000446	Nanomaterial type/IUC Substance/CAS	CAS	
Activity classification	N.A.	N.A.	Activity kind	
Current engineering control	N.A.	N.A.	Local control	
Parent material				
Lowest OEL (mg/m3)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Carcinogenic?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Reproductive hazard?	N.A.		N.A.	
Mutagen?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
dermal hazard?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
asthmagen?	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	
Nanoscale material				
Surface reactivity	N.A.	P-CHEM/Surface chemistry P-CHEM/Specific surface area	Volume specific surface area BET surface area	
Particle shape	Shape NPO_274	Protocols/SEM or TEM P-CHEM/Aspect ratio	N.A.	
Particle diameter	Particle diameter NPO_1539	Protocols/SEM Protocols/TEM P-CHEM/Particle size distribution	Particle size	
Solubility	Solubility ENM_0000089	P-CHEM/Water solubility	N.A.	
Carcinogenic?	Carcinogenicity ENM_0000029		N.A.	
Reproductive hazard?	Reproductive toxicity ENM_0000030		N.A.	
Mutagen?	Mutagenicity ENM_0000042	TOX/Genetic toxicity in vivo TOX/Genetic toxicity in vitro	N.A.	
dermal hazard?	Dermal toxicity ENM_0000025		N.A.	
asthmagen?	N.A.		N.A.	
Exposure probability				
Estimated amount of chemical used in one day (mg)	N.A.	N.A.	Used amount	
Dustiness	Dustiness ENM_9000003	P-CHEM/Dustiness	Dustiness	
Number of employees with the same exposure	N.A.	N.A.	Total number of workers exposed	
Frequency of operation	N.A.	N.A.	Number of shift per day	
Operation duration	N.A.	N.A.	Total activity duration in shift	

Annex 3. Database linking level

Here the level at which the database should be linked to specific tools for the SIA is discussed by using, as an example, some fields that Stoffenmanager nano (STMn) requires as input parameters. These input parameters are matched to specific endpoints, assays and results from the NanoReg2 database. The parameters derived from STMn are not exhaustive nor are the possible endpoints, assays and results in the database that can be linked to these parameters. The column referring to database queries represent 4 different levels at which the link of parameters in the tool can be made to actual data in the database.

1. The first level is on endpoints such as: size/ shape or genotoxicity etc. and provides a possible user with the relevant endpoints investigated that match with the meaning of the specific parameters in the tool (in this case STMn).
2. The second level provides the actual assays that are relevant for this specific input parameter from the NanoReg2 database which match with the meaning of the parameter in the tool.
3. The third level provides the results of the relevant assays **without** analysis of the results with regards to the input that the tool requires (such is the aspect ratio larger or smaller than 3:1).
4. The fourth level provides the results of the relevant assays **with** analysis of the results with regards to the input that the tool requires (such is the aspect ratio larger or smaller than 3:1).

With each increasing level the user is provided with more relevant information but the effort for the developers to link the tool to the database increases. At level 4 the tool could be filled with an automatic program interface linking the tool to the database.

What levels is reasonably achievable in the project?

What level is necessary in the project?

It was agreed during a telco on Work package 3 that the first level of detail is sufficient for the NanoReg2 project. A step towards the second level of detail has been made as well.

Input parameter	Clear description of STMn meaning	LEVEL of database query			
		1. General database endpoint query Provides the relevant endpoints that need reviewing	2. General database assay queries Provides the relevant experiments that needs reviewing	3. Database assays results queries Provides the results that need comparing	4. Database analysis result Provides actual answer to user
Step 1: General					
Name risk assessment					
Source domain					
Step 2: Product characteristics					
Product name	Give the product an own name	n/a	n/a		n/a
Product appearance (state)	The options for the product appearance depend on the selected source domain.				
Name nanocomponent	Give the nano component a name				
Dustiness	What is the dustiness of the product				
Moisture content	Indicate the moisture content of the product. The moisture content influences the extent to which the product is released.	n/a	n/a		n/a
Exact concentration percentage	Here you can enter the exact concentration of the nano component in the product as percentage				
Fibers	Does the product contain fibers / fiber like particles?	Output Material/particle_type	Output Material/particle_type	Output Material/particle_type	Output Material/particle_type = fiber/nanofiber/nanotube/needle
Length: diameter of the fiber (aspect ratio)	Aspect ratio >=3:1	Output Endpoint_options = shape	Output Endpoint_options = shape Assay_option = TEM	Output Endpoint_options = shape Assay_option = TEM Output Dimension/size_measurement = mean aspect ratio mode aspect ratio median aspect	Output Dimension/size_measurement = mean aspect ratio > 3 or mean aspect ratio < 0.33 mode aspect ratio > 3 or mode aspect ratio < 0.33 or median aspect ratio > 3 or median aspect ratio < 0.33 or
	Aspect ratio <3:1	Output Endpoint_options = shape	Output Endpoint_options = shape Assay_option = TEM	Output Endpoint_options = shape Assay_option = TEM Output Dimension/size_measurement = mean aspect ratio mode aspect ratio median aspect	Output Dimension/size_measurement = mean aspect ratio < 3 or mean aspect ratio > 0.33 mode aspect ratio < 3 or mode aspect ratio > 0.33 or median aspect ratio < 3 or median aspect ratio > 0.33 or
	>= 5000nm/unknown	Output Endpoint_options = size	Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = TEM	Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = TEM	Output dimension/size_measurement = Mean ecd >= 5000 nm or Mode ecd >= 5000 nm or Median ecd >= 5000 nm
			Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = DLS	Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = DLS Z-ave hydrodynamic diameter Peak intensity	Output dimension/size_measurement = Z-ave hydrodynamic diameter >= 5000 nm Peak at lowest size >= 5000 nm

	< 5000 nm/unknown	Output Endpoint_options = size	Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = TEM	Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = TEM Output Dimension/ size_measurement = mean aspect ratio mode aspect ratio median aspect	Output dimension/ size_measurement = Mean ecd < 5000 nm or Mode ecd < 5000 nm or Median ecd < 5000 nm
			Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = DLS	Output Endpoint_options = size Assay_option = DLS Z-ave hydrodynamic diameter Peak intensity	Output dimension/ size_measurement = Z-ave hydrodynamic diameter < 5000 nm Peak at lowest size < 5000 nm
Inhalation Hazard	Unknown				
	Mutagenic (and possibly carcinogenic) and/or sensitizing;	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = DNA strand breaks	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = DNA strand breaks NOAEL LOAEL BMD Etc.	<i>dependent on various conditions e.g. organism/ exposure route/ dose-response/ etc.</i> NOAEL > ... LOAEL > ... BMD > ... Etc.
			Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = gammaH2Ax	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = gammaH2Ax NOAEL LOAEL BMD Etc.	<i>dependent on various conditions e.g. organism/ exposure route/ dose-response/ etc.</i> NOAEL > ... LOAEL > ... BMD > ... Etc.
			Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = Micronucleus	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = Micronucleus NOAEL LOAEL BMD Etc.	<i>dependent on various conditions e.g. organism/ exposure route/ dose-response/ etc.</i> NOAEL > ... LOAEL > ... BMD > ... Etc.
			Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = Pig-A gene mutation	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = Pig-A gene mutation NOAEL LOAEL BMD Etc.	<i>dependent on various conditions e.g. organism/ exposure route/ dose-response/ etc.</i> NOAEL > ... LOAEL > ... BMD > ... Etc.
			Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = Swiss roll	Output Endpoint_options = Genotoxicity Assay_options = Swiss roll NOAEL LOAEL BMD Etc.	<i>dependent on various conditions e.g. organism/ exposure route/ dose-response/ etc.</i> NOAEL > ... LOAEL > ... BMD > ... Etc.
	Carcinogenic (not mutagenic), reprotoxic and/ or very toxic				
	toxic, corrosive and/or respiratory allergens				
	harmful and/or irritating				
	non hazardous				